

POST-PANDEMIC SUPERVISION: A FUTURISTIC FRAMEWORK

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ABSTRACT

The researcher conducted this study to offer ways for English coordinators and teachers to advocate for education about and in the future. It introduced prospect-positive supervision and teaching futures manipulation and provided a framework to challenge traditional practices and promote strategic and futures-oriented conversations within the education sector. Semi-structured questions were used to gather the supervisors' and teachers' experiences in supervisory practices and teaching and learning strategies through interviews and focus group interviews. The questions were categorized into four CLA layers: Litany, Systemic, World-view, and Myth/Metaphors. Selected English coordinators and English teachers from public and private schools in Davao City were interviewed. The result enabled to recreate supervisory policies and develop renewed teaching practices suitable to the changing society. The metaphors created were supervision is *an exam* and English teaching and learning is *a globe*. These metaphors became the basis for open discussion and help foresight practitioners in individual research or workshop settings as they perform their duties and restructure educational policies in supervision and teaching-learning the English language. It also led to the co-created futures in education as the "*school of virtual reality*", where AI-generated (supervision) and metaverse (teaching and learning) play an explicit role in supervision and the English teaching and learning process.

Keywords: *Causal Layered Analysis, English language, futures studies, metaphors, supervision and teaching*

INTRODUCTION

Supervision is technical, educational, and moral support given to teachers. Its pivotal role is improving instruction and engaging teachers in a dialogue to improve teaching and learning. Before the pandemic, instructional supervisors performed their duties based on different instructional and supervisory models (Hurry & Russel, 2022). However, the usual practices done by English instructional supervisors and English teachers were changed because of the pandemic. English supervisors' role is essential to ensure learning happens inside the classroom. English teachers must be updated with the pedagogies that ensure learning occurs. English supervisors should also be up-to-date to give training and support services and evaluate teachers' performance according to regulative rules and programs (Kayaoglu, 2012).

The changes brought about by the sudden impact of the COVID-19 pandemic have shown that education needs to be flexible and adaptable to the changing world's different contexts and needs (UNESCO, 2020). The closure of schools has led the academe to use technology, different media, digital platforms, and connectivity in ways not foreseen even decades ago (Inayatullah, 2021).

Responding to the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic, the Department of Education (DepEd) designed the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP), DepEd Order No. 12, s., 2020. It contained the direction for basic education, implementing guidelines and directives, operationalized programs, activities, and projects, and continuing the teaching and learning processes. One of the inputs of the BE-LCP was the use of Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs). These MELCs served as the bases for curating Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) and other learning materials during the pandemic (DepEd, 2020).

The learning environment had become diverse and encompassed, the physical classroom shifted to the cyber world, and the home became the school (DepEd, 2020). As education continues amidst the pandemic, several problems have arisen because of this sudden shift. First, was the disengaged supervision due to a lack of or limited interaction with the teaching-learning process. Second, was the teachers' need for prior exposure to online learning and distance learning modality, technological knowledge, and pedagogical knowledge (Lie *et al.*, 2020). Third, learners were not satisfied with continuing online learning since they needed help to realize the expected progress in language learning (Mahyoob, 2020).

The physical closure of schools and the use of online or distant modalities have confused academic leaders. They needed to prepare to oversee a different delivery of instruction (Brock *et al.*, 2021). The pedagogical and instructional practices were disconnected from the supervision of leaders, and supervisors could no longer "catch up" due to limited interaction (Mette, 2020). In addition, the sudden shift to distance learning forced everyone to continue with academic instruction with no or limited preparations regarding facilities, teachers' capacity, and students-parents' readiness (Lie *et al.*, 2020).

With all the ruckus on school personnel's supervision and teaching tasks, language teachers, in particular, had pointed out several problems. First, learners need to grasp a good foundation in language learning; however, the students' outputs failed to meet the desired quality due to limited interaction. Second, implementing English language learning was given little attention because school leaders and teachers mainly focused on adapting and using technology in conducting classes rather than performing the teaching-learning processes. Since most subjects used English as the medium of instruction, English played a significant role in helping these learners comply with the academic requirements regardless of the subject.

Nevertheless, with all these happenings, supervisors and educators see the "futures" of English language supervision, and the teaching and learning processes linked to the DepEd's (2020) Learning Continuity Plan's (LCP) three interconnected capacities: "innovation, agility, and synergy, which significantly linked to future." This research aimed to determine what the English language supervisors and teachers learned before and during the COVID-19 pandemic and to use these learnings in transitioning to the new educational "normal." This research offered ways for school heads/principals, English language coordinators, and teachers a glimpse about and into the future of instructional English language supervision and teaching and learning processes.

Research Questions

This study aimed to develop a framework for the future of instructional supervision and teaching English to foresee the future of this field during the post-pandemic. It also forecasted the changes it poses to the future caused by academic setup and policy changes. Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

- 1) How do English language supervisors describe the instructional supervision of the teaching and learning process before and during the pandemic?
- 2) How do English language teachers describe the teaching-learning process before and during the pandemic?
- 3) How do English supervisors describe the supervision styles they will adapt as they transition from the pandemic to the post-pandemic period?
- 4) How do English teachers describe the teaching and learning process as they transition from the pandemic to the post-pandemic period?
- 5) What do English supervisors and teachers believe, and how do these beliefs help them create their ideal future?
- 6) What metaphors could be developed to support the futures of supervision and the teaching and learning English language environment?

METHODOLOGY

In this chapter, the researcher presents the research design, respondents, instruments, data-gathering procedure, and data analyses to answer the research questions.

Research Design

The study uses the Causal Layered Analysis (CLA), an approach and a technique used in foresight to shape the future. It includes the phenomena and their analyses at different depths and times according to the four levels: litany, systemic causes, worldview discourse, and myth/metaphor (Inayatullah, 2017). CLA can be used for groups, individuals, or oneself as a stand-alone method. It ensures that the researcher is aware and reflective of her or his prejudices. It can also do the following: (1) expand the range and richness of situations, (2) appeal to a broader range of individuals since it is non-textual and uses the poetic expression in making foresight, (3) promote different ways of accompanying interests among participants, (4) distinguish and layer participants, (5) move the discussion to a more profound and marginal rather than obvious, (6) allow different transformative actions, (7) lead to the procedure that may be informed through layers of analysis, (8) lead to authentic, sustainable solutions, (9) develop short, medium, and long-term future, and (10) use different worldviews to understand the future and decide on a preferred one.

This research design is appropriate for this study since it gathered the respondents' experiences based on their accounts before and during the pandemic. It included the policies, practices, challenges encountered, the changes and adaptability to the sudden shift of learning modality, their values and beliefs as they moved forward to perform their respective duties, and the metaphor or myth that served as their ideal lived future. It increases the different views, and the participants can readily accept that the world is experiencing changes. Moreover, the CLA requires a wide-ranging literature review and an understanding of the four layers. Shown in **Table 1** are the functions of CLA, particularly in this research which are, mapping the future, creating the preferred one, and mapping the leading to a transformed one.

Table 1

Uses of CLA in a study (Inayatullah, Causal Layered Analysis, 2017).

Function	Result
Mapping the present/future	It prevents worldview blindness and creates whole-of-worldview and narrative solutions.
Create a preferred future	Moves from how things are to the desired future and enhances the visioning process.
Mapping Leading to a transformed future	Includes multiple positions plus a mapping leading to a transformed future transformed or integrated future.

To get the desired information, the questions were crafted and categorized based on the Causal Layered Analysis. CLA was a foresight methodology used to interpret various issues, revealing the underlying causality and unconscious bases. It opened up new conceptual spaces where alternatives to the existing norms are imagined and explored, allowing transformative actions (Simone, 2004). It helped deepen the understanding of

issues using the four-process: litany, systematic causes, worldview, and myth/metaphor (Inayatullah, 2019; Davidson, 2020). It explored deep myths and new litanies based on different viewpoints and use them in implementing new strategies that address problems. It explored connections between past, present, and foresighted future practices by integrating the theoretical understanding of future discourses and drawing upon experiences based on the context and practices the respondents had gone through in their respective fields (Inayatullah, 2017).

Figure 1 shows the CLA in qualitative data analysis in which the study utilized the CLA layers as the primary research framework. It is a stand-alone method (Talebian & Talebian, 2018), and claims to dig deep into how the participants foresee the future. Moreover, it brought scope and richness to thinking, helping with considering knowledge-related practices and moving conversation naturally from obvious to deeper levels (Talebian & Talebian, 2018). Moreover, this “futures study” follows the “deepening” using narratives, like deep stories, to make this fourth layer (metaphor) clear and practical (Milojevic & Inayatullah, 2015).

Shown in **Figure 1** were the stages that guided the researcher in analyzing the data gathered.

Figure 1. The CLA in qualitative data analysis (Tapio & Heinonen, 2018).

Respondents

Shown in **Table 2** are the respondents of the study for the qualitative data. It is composed of the following: four (4) English coordinators or master teachers in English from public schools and three (3) English coordinators/academic heads from private schools who have been a supervisor for at least three years; four (4) English teachers from public school and four (4) English teachers from private schools who have been teaching for at least three years.

Table 2

The English Coordinator and the Teacher respondents.

Participants from public and private schools	Age bracket	Years of Service
English Coordinator A	30-45 yrs. old	3 years up
English Coordinator B		
English Coordinator C		
English Coordinator D		
English Coordinator E		
English Coordinator F		
English Teacher A	25-35 yrs. old	
English Teacher B		
English Teacher C		
English Teacher D		
English Teacher E		
English Teacher F		
English Teacher G		

The respondents were identified randomly, regardless of their gender. However, the ages for teachers were from 25-35 years old, while the ages of the coordinator/supervisor ranged from 30-45 years old. These people were considered millennials, born between 1981-1997. They were the first generation to reach adulthood in the new millennium, which indicated that they experienced the rapid changes followed by the later generations (Frey, 2018). Moreover, it was made sure that the respondents were exposed to their field of work before and during the pandemic so that they could share valuable insights and share experiences for this study.

Research Instrument

This study's main instruments were a semi-structured interview crafted using the CLA model and a simple researcher-made survey questionnaire. Through individual interviews, the semi-structured questions gather the supervisors' and teachers' litany, systemic causes, worldview discourse, and myth/metaphor in supervisory practices and teaching and learning strategies. These questions were used during the individual interviews and Focus Group Discussion (FGD). The survey form was crafted after the individual interviews. It contained the metaphors from the respondents. Meanwhile, the

participants ranked the metaphors using Google Forms to find out what metaphor resonated in the group.

Individual interviews. Semi-structured interviews contained several vital questions that help defined the explored areas. The researcher may have adjusted and changed the direction of the questions (Alamri, 2019). Open-ended questions facilitate faster interviews, making them easier to analyze and compare. In addition, this method allowed the researcher to collect open-ended data and explore the participants' feelings, thoughts, and beliefs about the topic (DeJonckheere & Vaughn, 2019). It also emphasized linguistic data, distinguishing the issues from the respondents' perspective in a particular area. It also played a significant role in getting open-ended details.

Moreover, it was substantial for assessing views, perspectives, and thoughts and helpful in collecting information from different participants (Alamri, 2019). Individual interviews promoted spontaneity since the respondents did not have the chance to change their answers or responses. These answers were more reliable and informative.

Focus Group Discussion (FGD). FGD originated in Sociology (Mishra, 2016) and is a type of in-depth interview done in a group. The influence of participants on each other through their ideas and contributions during the discussion was present. The moderator led the discussion, in this case, the researcher. The discussion was outlined beforehand to ensure all topics were covered (Mishra, 2016). Group discussion created a synergy effect on participants, and when there was limited opportunity for data collection, FGD was done to compare the result to individual interviews. Moreover, it was utilized to collect high-quality evidence and can be a source to inspect internal views and emotions (Akyildiz & Ahmed, 2021).

Using CLA to outline the questions. The questions followed the four (4) CLA layers: litany, systemic, worldview, and myth/metaphors. Each category corresponded to the statement of the problems and a set of probing questions.

Litany, the first layer. It is the unquestioned view of reality (Inayatullah, 2014). The questions specifically revolved around the instructional supervision activities of coordinators and teaching strategies of teachers before and during a pandemic, it tackles the observation forms they used in line with the standards that the teachers were following in teaching English, and how things in their work changed or modified when the pandemic occurred. These were the non-negotiables and the actual happenings based on the policies and changes in the practices the participants had encountered.

Systematic, the second layer. These were the system/social issues where the academic analysis of frequent causes is investigated. The data of the litany was explained and questioned at this level (Inayatullah, 2014). The questions revolved around the critical aspects that challenged them during the pandemic, which they consider helpful in the post-pandemic. They were also asked about their preparations during the transition and how these preparations helped them face the future.

Worldview, the third layer. This refers to deep beliefs and values. The respondents were asked about their educational philosophies and values that made them continue their work amidst their challenges. Participants unconsciously held to their ideologies at this level, and their discursive assumptions were unpacked based on their accounts in the first and second levels (Inayatullah, 2014). This level prepared the respondent for the last level, the myth/metaphors.

Myth/ Metaphors. The questions were about the ideal future of the coordinators and teachers in the English teaching and learning process. It also discovered the depth of meanings by asking the respondents to create a metaphor that describes their ideal future: for coordinators, the metaphor for English Instructional supervision, and for the teachers, the metaphor for English teaching and learning. In this fourth and last layer, the rhetoric or creative representatives of preferred lived futures, were placed (Riedy, 2008, cited by Carballo, 2018).

Guided by the linear process of CLA (Simone, 2004), the questions were reviewed, revised, and regrouped until they reached their final version. The linear process of CLA:

- 1) *The vertical gaze, uncovering causality, was used to expose the underlying cause of the issue.*
- 2) *Horizontal gazes, discovering alternatives was about asking questions that allow one to discover/uncover other ways of knowing.*
- 3) *Re-envisioning the myth and metaphor was the initial re-forming of an issue from the myth/metaphor as an image/story of the problem to the imagining and defining of ideal alternative imageries/stories.*
- 4) *Recasting the issue/problem and defining possible solutions by considering the causalities and discovering ways with a preferred solution.*
- 5) *Selecting and documenting solutions at each level (Causal layered analysis: A 'cookbook' approach page 3)*

The development of the instrument. The instrument was revised according to the suggestion of the validators and after the conduct of the pilot testing. It ensured that the questions asked to fit each level of the CLA and that the researcher could get crucial data from the respondents' answers.

There were revisions made to the interview questions. The first version consisted of five statements of the problems and the probing questions. The four (4) validators gave their inputs to improve the questionnaire, especially the probing queries. The second version consisted of five statements about the problems, but the probing questions were revised per the validators' advice. After the pilot testing, with two (2) English teachers and one (1) English coordinator, some probing questions were removed, and some were revised. In the third version, the questions were revisited as advised by one of the questionnaire validators, Dr. Sohail Inayatullah, to ensure that there should be a question(s) that would lead to the respondents' world views or their beliefs or values; this resulted in version 4 that contained six statements of the problems to fit into the four layers/levels of CLA properly.

Interrater Reliability. Interrater reliability refers to the scope to which two or more experts agree. It was a test of consistency of measurement (Fink, 2010). Interrater reliability also

called *interobserver reliability*, helped measure people's agreement on the same thing by reading the transcribed responses (Middleton, 2023). After the pilot testing, the transcription of the interviews was submitted to field experts to test its reliability. In this study, three (3) inter-raters assess the data. A rating or score sheet contained the category of questions (based on CLA). The inter-raters were given a copy of the pilot interview transcript. This activity aimed to minimize the subjectivity of the data. The inter-rater mean average is 4.

The metaphors. Metaphors provide a window to the construction of knowledge and insight. It was used as an analogy that can enhance understanding (Groth & Bergner, 2005). Metaphors can also be derived from narratives that go beyond conventional issues. In this research, they considered the unconscious and emotive side of the participants, followed by “deepening,” which enhanced the broader aspect of the analysis while suggesting explanations for the presented dimensions of the problems through a researcher-made metaphor. These metaphors were gathered through the final questions during the individual interview and were arranged in a Google form. During the FGD, the respondents were asked to rank them (Inayatullah, 2019).

The metaphors that were ranked according to the participants’ most preferred future served as the destination to achieve the desired future (Rogerson, 2021 & Inayatullah *et al.*, 2016). Myths/ metaphors are more challenging to access than simple perspectives. In this case, the participants were asked to compare the future to an idea or a thing. Expected answers were symbols or material things directly associated with the future. It included proverbs, slogans, idioms, religious texts, *etc.* After this, a consolidated metaphor was created, to describe both (supervision and teaching-learning English), further, the metaphors were expounded, resulting in the metaphors of English supervision, teaching, and learning in 5 years and 10 years. Aside from the CLA table, images were also used in this case.

Data Gathering Procedure

This qualitative study collected data through in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. All interviews were conducted through a video conference to adhere to safety protocols against COVID-19. The following steps were observed in conducting the study:

Seeking permission. The researcher sent a request letter for permission to the DepEd’s Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) of Davao. The permission was subsequently granted; it allowed the sending of permission letters and endorsements to the public-school principals, school heads/directors, and principals for private schools. The school heads’ approval led the researcher to identify the participants with the assistance of the school principal and the administrative assistant.

Securing permission from the participants. After identifying the participants, a letter of permission and an informed consent form were sent to each respondent. It was to ensure that the participants had agreed to be in the study and that they understood what it was

all about. The ethical consent also contained complete information about the study and the protocol to adhere to gather the data. The signed informed consent letter was retrieved before the individual interview was held.

Conducting in-depth interviews. Observing the COVID-19 health and safety precautions and other conditions asked by the SDS of Davao City, all interviews were done using google meet and Zoom meetings. The interviews lasted for 30-40 minutes per respondent. Meanwhile, the FGDs were done within 60-90 minutes per group. Each session was recorded with the permission of the participants.

Transcribing the recorded interview responses. Interviews were digitally recorded with the respondents' consent. Transcription of the digital recordings was done to ensure quality.

Data Analysis

After conducting both semi-structured interviews and FGDs on the identified groups, the researcher did the transcription to take the interview contents and effectively analyze them.

The data collected used the CLA qualitative data analysis. These were analyzed using the CLA in qualitative data analysis steps shown in **Table 3**. *First*, familiarizing the material; in this study, the transcribed responses of the respondents. *Second*, the summarizing of data in the litany and systemic causes. *Third*, is the generating of initial codes. *Fourth*, is the interpreting of the codes and finding the themes or labels. *Fifth*, is the categorizing of the worldview.

Lastly, imagery of the future using myth/metaphors. This fourth layer reflects the participants' emotional level experiences based on their worldview. The language was more precise, suggesting visual images and touching the heart instead of the mind (Inayatullah 2004). It presented different perspectives on the subjects and thus opened opportunities for further dialogues (Inayatullah, 2017).

Table 3

The CLA in Qualitative Data Analysis (Tapio & Heinonen, 2018).

- 1) Familiarizing the material.
 - 2) Condensing the material, litany, and systemic causes.
 - 3) Generating initial codes.
 - 4) Interpreting codes and finding themes.
 - 5) Categorizing: Finding horizontal alternatives, worldview
 - 6) Imaging the future, myth/metaphor
-

Tables were prepared for each group of responses to answer the statement of the problems. Each table contained the labels/themes from the analyzed data. Meanwhile, the ranked metaphors during the FGD helped identify the preferred lived future for supervisors and teachers. Afterward, the "deepening" was done through researcher-made metaphors and illustrations.

RESULTS

The presentation proceeds in this sequence: (a) English language supervisors' instructional supervision before and during the pandemic; (b) English language teachers' teaching process before and during the pandemic; (c) supervision styles in the post-pandemic period; (d) teaching and learning process in the post-pandemic period; (e) English supervisors and English teachers' beliefs and values; and (f) metaphor developed to support the English language future supervision, and the teaching and learning process.

English Language Supervisors' Instructional Supervision Before and During the Pandemic

Table 4 summarizes English coordinators' supervision practices before and during the pandemic at the litany level. The term "*used future*" identifies outdated narratives created in the past, and this reality has been challenged by changes (Milojevic & Inayatullah, 2015).

Table 4

The Litany of English Coordinator's Supervision Practices Before and During the Pandemic

<i>Litany Level</i>	Practices
Used Future (<i>Pre-pandemic</i>)	Supervision based on provisions Securing quality teaching-learning
The changing environment (<i>Pandemic</i>)	Reconciliation of old ways Adaptation of Technology

English Language Teachers' Teaching Processes Before and During the Pandemic

Table 5 presents the litany level for English teachers' practices before and during the pandemic.

Table 5

The Litany of English Teachers' Practices Before and During the Pandemic

<i>Litany Level</i>	Practices
Used Future (<i>Pre-pandemic</i>)	Implementing differentiated instruction Interconnecting Teacher-student
The changing environment (<i>Pandemic</i>)	Multitasking of teachers Compromising academic integrity

Giving Inauthentic assessments
 Providing student help
 Failing value formation
 Combining Traditional and
 technology

Supervision Styles in the Post-Pandemic Period

Table 6 focused on the changes and adaptability of the coordinators as they described their experiences in preparing for the transition from the pandemic to the post-pandemic period.

Table 6

The English Language Coordinators' Supervision Styles from Pandemic to Post-Pandemic.

<i>Systemic Level</i>	Supervision styles
Pandemic	Autocratic supervision Bureaucratic supervision
Post-pandemic	Laissez-faire – the free spirit Democratic supervision

Teaching and Learning Processes in the Post-Pandemic Period

Shown in **Table 7** are the teachers' preparations and adaptability from the pandemic to the post-pandemic.

Table 7

The Teachers' Preparation and Adaptability from Pandemic to Post-Pandemic and the Future.

<i>Systemic Level</i>	Preparations and adaptability
Pandemic	Marrying technology Upskilling of teachers
Post-pandemic	Readying for the hard battle

The English supervisors' values and beliefs to help recreate the future

Table 8 summarizes English coordinators' values and beliefs to recreate the future. This section examines the coordinators' values and beliefs that inclined them to continue performing their instructional leadership duties. It consisted of their current and future perspectives. Also, the coordinators have perceptions that they believe in that align with the values and ideas of their teachers. They believe in being responsible for the students under their care. The coordinators expressed their responsibilities to the teachers, believing that when teachers were properly handled, it would reciprocate to the learners. Below are the manifestations of the English supervisors as they relay their beliefs and values to help recreate their desired futures.

Table 8*The English Language Coordinators' Values and Beliefs to Recreate the Future.*

Values and Beliefs	
<i>Worldview Level</i>	Quality performance=, quality learning Progressive mindset and open-mindedness Adaptability Act of service

Shown in **Table 9** are English teachers' values and beliefs to recreate the future.

Table 9*The CLA of English Teachers' Values and Beliefs to Recreate the Future.*

Values and Beliefs	
<i>Worldview Level</i>	Commitment Love Competence Hope

The CLA of English supervision and teaching and learning process

The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) released the Journal on Co-creating Educational Futures: Contradictions between the emerging future and the walled past. This paper presented a simple future-thinking intervention process for alternative strategies and illustrated foresight in education and beyond. Moreover, its provided vital issues within the UNESCO 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and Futures of Education initiatives (Inayatullah, 2020). In summary, **Tables 10** and **11** present the CLA levels of English supervision and CLA on English teaching and learning.

Table 10*CLA on English Supervision.*

CLA Level	The changing environment (Post-pandemic)
<i>Litany</i>	Adaptation of Technology
<i>Systemic</i>	Laissez-faire, the free spirit Democratic Supervision
<i>Worldview (Values and beliefs)</i>	Quality performance is quality learning
<i>Metaphors</i>	An exam/ a test

Table 11*CLA on English Teaching and Learning.*

CLA Level	<i>The changing environment (Post-pandemic)</i>
<i>Litany</i>	Combining traditional and technological teaching and learning
<i>Systemic</i>	Readying for the brutal battle
<i>Worldview (Values and beliefs)</i>	Bridging the learning gaps Commitment Love Competence
<i>Metaphors</i>	Hope A globe

DISCUSSION

English Language Supervisors' Instructional Supervision Before and During the Pandemic

Even before the pandemic, the supervisors already experienced difficulties in performing their job as instructional leaders, with all the tasks like year-round supervision, checking of lesson plans and test questions, conducting research, implementing school policies, making sure the teachers receive assistance and training, and uplifting oneself by further studies and leadership training as part of instructional supervisory provisions. They perform mid-administration duties and have specific roles in schools, especially in heading the English department through initiating programs that will benefit the students' English language learning, ensuring quality teaching-learning experience.

When the challenges brought by the pandemic confronted supervisors, they encountered many problems, including implementing the usual protocols and policies prescribed by the DepEd. However, the pandemic gave them the idea that the traditional ways have to be aligned with the sudden changes. The experience made the educational sectors see the need for ICT training of teachers to adapt to the current learning modes (Othman & Mydin, 2022).

Everyone fumbled in the dark and felt they were lost. Their fear of the "unknown" almost lasted a year, trying to find out what could be done and should be done with the problems that arose during the health crisis, and their role as supervisors from implementing rules and regulations as mandated by DepEd. Orders and memo and or institutional policies for private institutions to become lenient and flexible gave them the idea to change the paradigm from being authoritative leaders and sticking to the rule to being warm and considering leaders as part of the success of the changes brought by the transition.

Below are the manifestations of their experiences as they transformed from the pre-pandemic to the pandemic period and how they made their way to succeed in every challenge they faced as English supervisors.

Monitoring and checking of teachers' lesson plans, tables of specifications (TOS), test papers, and other documents related to the teaching and learning processes were conducted to supervise the teaching and learning environment before the pandemic. The coordinators claimed they mainly focused on classroom visits to ensure the delivery of content lessons in the teaching-learning environment. Classroom observation and monitoring were essential practices performed by the coordinators. It is the effort to develop teachers to achieve the teaching-learning process's standards and objectives (Othman & Mydin, 2022). The coordinators shared their pre-pandemic class observation practices:

Before the pandemic, our protocol was an announced classroom observation" (Zeus).

We have pop-in and formal visits. We pass by the corridors focusing on classroom management" (Hermes).

Class observations were done in the physical classroom before the pandemic. We call it non-formal and formal classroom observations" (Ares).

Classroom monitoring and observations for the public schools were conducted using a standard evaluation form issued by the DepEd. In comparison, private institutions adhere to the forms from accrediting bodies like the Private Education Assistance Committee (PEAC) and the Philippine Accrediting Association of Schools, Colleges, and Universities (PAASCU) and school-formulated forms. The private school academic supervision practice is categorized as follows: pop-in visits, coordinators staying inside the classroom for 15-20 minutes, non-rated clinical observations, or structured observations. It is done to improve the teaching-learning processes; constructive feedback is followed so teachers will know what is best and what to work on with their class strategies. The rated formal observation served as the basis for performance evaluation.

The purpose of visiting the teaching spaces was to see what was happening inside the classrooms and to check whether the teachers delivered the standards in the teaching and learning process. Furthermore, the supervisory program updates the teachers' knowledge on recent advances; update skills, attitudes, and approaches to new techniques and strategies; enable teachers to apply changes to the curriculum; exchange information and expertise; and help struggling teachers to become more efficient and effective on their craft (OECD [Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development], 2009).

School leadership is about class observations and changing the school culture, setting goals, monitoring student achievements, and confronting new challenges to meet expectations and standards (Gamage *et al.*, 2009). There should be immediate feedback after class observations to inform the teachers if they met the standards. A post-conference is scheduled to communicate the supervisors' comments after class observations. It is part of the coaching-mentoring program. Meanwhile, the teachers' performance rating is based on the result of the final or year-end class observation conducted. The statement of one coordinator supported this:

... post-conference followed. The end of the school year is the final observation. Each teacher is rated, and the result is included in the 201 files as part of the teacher appraisal (Zeus).

To guarantee quality instruction, the coordinators used indicators and checked whether classroom activities aligned with the vision, mission, core values, and the learners' needs. They also checked whether the lessons and skills taught applied to real-life situations. Particularly in language teaching, they looked for the teachers' efficiency in using the language, grammar, constructing questions, and student-teacher and student-student interaction. Class interaction allows students to exchange ideas, feelings, insights, opinions, and others (Eisenring & Margana, 2019). The coordinators confirmed this when they shared:

There is a set of indicators that we used, speech and learning process, and the alignment of teaching practices to our school's vision, mission, goals, and core values. We want to ensure that the lessons are applied in real context or situations (Zeus).

... they have to be communicatively competitive in class, a model, and use and speak the language so that students will follow (Athena).

... we look for the usage of grammar, pronunciation, and the way they construct the questions and interaction between students and teachers. The students also are encouraged to speak the language (Hermes).

I always look at two-way interaction. The teacher and learner interaction. I need to see that the students develop their communication skills, especially speaking and writing (Ares).

According to Hwa *et al.*, (2020), aligning instruction levels to the student's goals and needs is essential to further learning. It implied that human learning is cumulative. Since memory has a minimal capacity for processing new information, the brain expands and capacitates when building on long-term knowledge. This long-term knowledge involved essential lifelong learning. Likewise, the teachers should ensure that the learners have prior knowledge before teaching new skills (Hwa *et al.*, 2020).

The alignment of the educational philosophy and teaching-learning process directly implements educational theory, underpinning the learners' everyday life (Bim-Bad & Egorova, 2016). This process is essential in monitoring and evaluating the teaching and learning process. The DepEd's vision is to produce Filipino learners who love their country and whose competencies contribute to the nation's building. Its mission is to protect and promote the right of every Filipino learner to get quality, culture-based, and right-to-complete primary education. *Maka-Diyos, Maka-tao, Makakalikasan, and Makabansa's* core values helped the department achieve the education mandate established through Republic Act 9155 (DepEd Order No. 1, s., 2003). All of these are part of the evaluation or checklist for quality assurance.

Before the pandemic, the observation had nine (9) indicators. These are (1) application of content knowledge within and across subject areas, (2) using of mother tongue, Filipino, and English, in facilitating learning, (3) using of verbal and non-verbal classroom

strategies, (4) establishing safe and secure learning space, (5) promoting fairness, respect, and care, (6) maintaining a learning environment that nurtures and inspire learners, (7) applying varied strategies that maintain learning environments to motivate learners, (8) designing, adapting, and implementing strategies which were responsive to diverse learner's needs, and (9) adapting and using culturally appropriate strategies to address the needs of indigenous learners (DepEd Resource, 2021).

The coordinators use these indicators in observing classes. Additionally, grounding on the English Curriculum Guide (DepEd, 2016), the LAMC aimed to produce graduates with the following competencies: communicative, grammatical, sociolinguistic, discourse, and strategic (K to 12 English Curriculum Guide, 2016). It also stressed multiliteracies, which meant recognizing many kinds of literacy at work and within society, and that English is the most widely used medium of communication in different curriculum content areas.

Private schools faced a fast turnover of teachers. Beginning teachers work in private institutions to gain experience before transferring to public schools for higher salaries (Buenaventura, 2013). With the rapid change of people in an institution, leaders' and novice teachers' support was needed to help them perform their job effectively (Okinyi et al., 2015). Nevertheless, even before the pandemic, the challenges were already put on the shoulders of the coordinators since the language teachers had to be guided, especially those newly retained. When asked what areas are observed when doing class visits, one coordinator said:

Depending on the needs, especially newly retained, and those non-English majors, from time to time, they are observed until we are confident that they can perform well (Zeus).

Zeus had been an English coordinator for over three years in a private school. He also shared that he made sure to talk to the teacher after observation on the areas for improvement. His statement supported this:

We discuss and agree on what specific practices could be improved (Zeus).

Not only the indicators, particularly in language teaching, get attention. The teachers are also observed in their classroom management, the art of asking questions, and other areas. One coordinator supported this claim:

All areas are observed, like classroom management, the art of questioning, and the teaching-learning processes (Hermes).

The coordinators extended their task to informal talks to build rapport with the teacher and promote a good work relationship. Since they are confronted with adapting to complex environments by developing meaningful relationships with teachers to successfully manage the multifaceted contexts of schools (Lasater, 2016), they still do ways to establish relationships. After all, rapport made teachers feel peaceful and open to suggestions. It was one of the essential facets distinctive to human communication (Kapur, 2018). One coordinator stated:

There is also informal discussion aside from the post-conference, a pre-conference is also done. After the second month, we have the pop-in visits (Athena).

The English language coordinators performed these academic supervisions before the pandemic. However, on January 30, 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic was declared. It has affected businesses, the economy, and the lives of thousands of people (Cennimo, 2023). Education was not an exemption. Some students found a way to continue their education amidst the physical closure of schools; the disadvantaged students were shut down together with the schools (Schleicher & Reimers, 2020).

In the Philippines, the closure of schools was very procedural and challenging. The DepEd issued memorandums that covered the measures, background situation, initiation of the risk management team, medical referrals, health situation reports, and reduction of flu in schools (Ancho, 2021). The following section presents the challenges met by the English coordinators during the pandemic.

Supervision during the pandemic. The pandemic affected people's social and emotional well-being, and learning and educational development had severe effects (Brock *et al.*, 2021). It was supported by the claims of Tabassum *et al.*, (2022) that the most common problems of English teachers were due to the high ratio of student teachers in one class and the designation of teachers to multigrade classes. These scenarios were already difficult to handle, especially when schools diverted to distance learning modality. It entailed patience and resourcefulness on the part of the coordinator's supervisory tasks. As mentioned by a coordinator:

Yes! There were real changes, especially in the first year of the pandemic, when everybody was groping in the dark. I needed to adjust my responsibilities as the English Language coordinator (Athena).

The physical closure of schools and utilization of the online and distant delivery system have created critical issues for school leaders and their roles in instructional supervision (Brock *et al.*, 2021). Meanwhile, most schools with internet connectivity adopted blended learning, combining synchronous and asynchronous classes. A coordinator added:

We have virtual class observation, but it was not the same during pre-pandemic (Athena).

However, schools with students who have no access to an internet connection resorted to Self-Learning Modules (SLMs). It hampered the interaction between students and teachers. In addition, it also found problems in using the SLMs. These problems included but were not limited to poor quality delivery, excessive and demanding activities, and distractions in the home environment. Nevertheless, there were also positive effects. These were the development of students' independent learning and convenience (Hoyla, 2021).

Further, as reported by National Education Technology (2016), the digital divide continued to exist between learners who were using technology actively and creatively to support their learning and those who predominantly used technology for passive content consumption. There was a clear difference between full online classes or synchronous and online asynchronous modalities. The absence of these students in the blended learning brought a difference in the modality of the coordinators' supervision practices. However, despite the technology struggles, schools devised ways to monitor teachers during distance teaching-learning. A coordinator shared:

During online classes, we were offline, listening. Sometimes the observer gets in the online class (Hermes).

Still, many schools need access to or need help to be able to use technology in ways that can improve learning. Thomas (2016) argued that using technology to support learning has yet to be widely adopted by schools. Also, technological tools in management, such as computers, school websites, zoom calls, emails, *and others*, during the pandemic were used by supervisors as a channel of information (Ince, 2021). There appeared to be less supervision of people but more on managing information that needed dissemination to the whole community.

The coordinators still evaluate teachers' performance during the pandemic. It was through class demonstrations and online checking of papers. One coordinator shared that the teachers prefer to use Learning Action Cell Sessions (LAC) in class demonstrations since they need more confidence to do it online. Likewise, the coordinators' correct papers online, as claimed by some of the coordinators:

*Class observation shifted to class demos in the form of LAC sessions. There was no class observation with students but with teachers acting as students (Ares).
Teachers were not observed with actual students but with their fellow teachers who acted as students (Perseus).
... we assigned them to specific classrooms just like having their own classroom and advisory class (Hermes).
The giving of corrections to the teachers' papers, like modules, matrix, and TOS, during the first few months with the work-from-home setup, were done using the technology. We have Zoom calls and have the teacher share screen the document to avoid miscommunication. Even post-conference is done online or virtual (Athena).*

It was also mentioned during the FGD. It supports their claims that most seasoned teachers, even when they were good in face-to-face classes, needed help adapting to the online modality because they were used to traditional approaches. Even if some teachers had online classes since they were handling STE (Science and Technology Education) sections who had online classes, they still preferred the LAC sessions. One coordinator claimed that:

Although we have synchronous classes with students, we can choose what to use during observation through LAC session or the prerecorded video

lesson. However, most of them prefer the LAC session for the demo. I also notice that even if they choose that, they were quite hesitant since they feel inferior to some teacher participants” (Ares).

Othman and Mydin (2022) claimed that many teachers need more mastery of digital technology to support online and distance learning, thus requiring in-depth training on acquiring knowledge to implement the educational process. Consequently, the role of the coordinators and leaders in supervision is done online to maintain the quality of teaching by giving varied support to teachers, which includes the utilization of open educational resources online (Othman & Mydin, 2022).

Another adjustment was the communication between the coordinator and the teacher. Since they had work-from-home arrangements, the subject coordinators adapted the distance modality in supervision. It was a big challenge for everyone since not all were adept at using technology like Zoom, Google Meet, Cisco, Jitsi Meet, etc. During the distance supervision, the coordinators still found time to talk and communicate with their teachers online; thus, the practice of post-conference before the pandemic was continued. One of the coordinators narrated:

We have Zoom calls and have the teacher share screen the document (lesson plan or test questions) to avoid miscommunication. Even post-conference is done online or virtual (Athena).

Ariffin *et al.*, (2022) believe that English teachers should maintain a social presence in online learning. Even if all their teachers had synchronous classes, they were still monitored online; coordinators check if learning still occurs inside the virtual classrooms and if the students participate in teaching-learning activities. They also did in-person classroom observation with teachers who acted as students at least once a month. With this, the teachers can practice in-person classes while doing the distance learning modality. One coordinator shared the same but noticed how they enjoyed the activity. Coming from the testimony of one coordinator:

We assign 5 to 6 teachers to act as students during the teacher’s class demo. These teachers act according to their roles. The supervisor will assign someone to be naughty; one is the brightest, then another will act as a regular student. It could be funny, but we enjoyed doing it (Hermes).

As stated earlier in the DepEd memorandum, it was all procedural, and the supervisory side was left hanging during the first year of the pandemic. Coordinators needed clarification about their role since it needed to be defined clearly, and the modality change required different ways of supervision. A study conducted by Fendi *et al.*, (2021) argued that subject coordinators met several obstacles in conducting online-based supervision because of the absence of standard applications provided by the governing bodies. Aside from that, the coordinators brawled in their tasks, especially when the connectivity problem came into the picture. One coordinator shared:

... it is tough to look at the teachers if they deliver the lesson well because sometimes the internet connection is lost or poor (Athena).

Nevertheless, academic supervision was adequate during the pandemic by being resourceful, requiring teachers to report their teaching and learning activities using technology media, improving teachers' understanding and ability to utilize technology, and evaluating the learning process periodically. A coordinator expressed his opinion and said they tried their best to continue doing their job as supervisors:

It is challenging due to the fast change of modality. However, we thought of something we can still observe in classes. It goes with how the teacher discusses the lesson (Hermes).

The coordinator experienced difficulties monitoring classes, especially the teaching-learning process. Aside from the technological tools used, the situation called for professional growth for teachers. While online or distance learning posed negative and positive implications, it called for all teachers to be trained in teaching online (Esteron, 2021).

The facilitators' struggles were the teachers' lack of ability to do online-based learning, the limited ability of teachers to impose effective learning strategies through online media, and the teachers' difficulty in finding suitable media in the online learning processes. However, the coordinators still did the coaching-mentoring to help these struggling teachers (Fendi *et al.*, 2021). Still, this event calls for education officials to rethink the processes and strategies for guiding and providing feedback to teachers during such a critical time (Giffin, 2020).

The classroom observation tool (COT)-RPMS for teachers I-III (*Appendix S*) in the time of COVID-19 used the following indicators: (1) applying the content knowledge within and across subject areas, (2) using the mother tongue, Filipino, (3) and English in teaching learning proficiently, (4) using effectively the verbal and non-verbal communication strategies to support learning, establishing a safe and secured learning environment, and (5) maintaining the fairness, respect, and care in the learning environment. The other (3) three indicators were waived (DepEd Resource, 2021). The observation tools were also modified to fit the context. Public schools also focused on non-negotiables, as claimed by a couple of participants:

The indicators were reduced to nine (9). Of nine (9) indicators, only (five) 5 are non-negotiable. It means it must be performed in an actual or class simulation. The other four (4) indicators are observed using different means of verification like the lesson plan and instructional materials" (Perseus).

One coordinator supported this claim in this narration:

Yes, we used observation tools from the central office. During pre-pandemic, the tool had nine (9) indicators. However, during the pandemic time, the tool had only five (5) indicators (Ares).

Some private schools had adopted the observation tools given by accrediting associations, such as the Private Association Assistance Committee the Philippine

Accrediting Association of Schools, Colleges, and Universities or the existing observation forms were modified to fit the condition. Since schools had varied contexts, the observation tools were also modified according to the situation's needs. The statements of the coordinators support this claim:

*We have modified or changed our observation sheets entirely since the criteria would not fit anymore, that includes classroom management and others. There is the modification of the observation tool (Athena).
There are just some rewordings for the appropriateness of the modality. The teachers got the tools before the observation, so they know how they will be rated (Zeus).
Yes, we use the PEAC observation tool. During the pandemic, we adopted it (Hermes).*

The task of the coordinators also escalated. From monitoring, mentoring, and evaluating, they had to become technology proficient since not all of the teachers under them were tech-savvy. They obliged themselves to be at par and respond to the situation's needs. Brock *et al.*, (2021) support this claim, as they expressed that these subject coordinators and leaders needed the skills, abilities, and mindsets related to crisis leadership which was equally crucial for broad decision-making in teaching and learning. In addition, Rilliard (2020) suggested that most were adapting to the COVID-19 crisis, which involved finding solutions to different challenges. One coordinator also shared that his role during the pandemic spiraled from actual to virtual supervision.

During a pandemic, my role's scope is realized via a virtual platform, recorded, and scheduled (Hermes).

The coordinators also acknowledged that to help their teachers cope with the situation, they need to step ahead and learn technical skills to assist the teachers under their care. During the focus group discussion, one coordinator shared that he had to be a phase ahead of his teachers in terms of technology utilization.

As the head, I felt I am more responsible in helping my teachers in ICT, and I become more aware of the tech tools to use (Hermes).

Not all teachers were technology proficient. Most teachers needed to be more conscientiously using technology during face-to-face classes. When confronted with the unexpected health crisis and closure of physical schools, these teachers had difficulties delivering instruction using online applications and extension educational tools when schools implemented distance learning. Fendi *et al.*, (2021) claim that during the pandemic, teachers could not modernize teaching and learning processes through online media like google classroom, google meet, and Zoom and only gave assignments to students to support this assertion. The teachers who even used online meeting tools in conducting classes did not guarantee student engagement and participation since they just did lectures throughout the period. They need pedagogy to utilize different tools in conducting virtual instruction. One coordinator shared:

...they just do lectures when they can enrich it by technology. Like the poll, roller, wheel of names, but there are outstanding teachers who can enrich more on their instructions (Zeus).

Aside from a lack of IT mastery, there were many students to facilitate. According to Sieber (2005) as cited by Burch (2019), the number of students in an online class was ideally 12. Another was the internet connection constraints and difficulties in explaining materials that needed *whiteboard* materials. They also observed that some teachers performing well during face-to-face classes could have been more effective during online classes. They claimed a need to train teachers' ICT skills to properly perform their duty, not just to relay information and concepts but to process information using technology. The testimonies of two (2) coordinators support this assertion:

There are also good teachers in the face-to-face class but have difficulty adopting the modality (Zeus).

The need to sharpen teachers' ICT Skills is at its height (Hermes).

Nevertheless, Romanes and Viniegas (2018) found that Boomers (teachers born in 1946-1964) had taught critical thinking skills to an extent due to their experiences compared to younger generations like Generation X (1965-1981) and Generation Y (1981-1995); meanwhile, all these generational groups had no significant differences in collaboration teaching. Furthermore, since this era consists of Generation Z (1997-2012), teachers are open to innovations, teamwork, project orientation, and analytical thinking (Demirbilek *et al.*, 2022). It will be an excellent opportunity to face and solve the current challenges if the leaders properly facilitate this group of educators and develop a system that combines traditional and modern teaching methods, especially language arts.

To sum up, before the pandemic, the coordinators followed policies and procedures prescribed by the DepEd and private school system and accrediting bodies. They utilized standard classroom observation tools for classroom visits which involved pop-ins and clinical and formal observations. They also provide critical feedback and monitoring of paperwork such as TOS, test papers, lesson plans, and others. During the pandemic, the coordinators faced many challenges that brought difficulties in implementing their leadership roles. Many schools adopted blended learning, while most adopted the usage of SLMs, which hampered the physical interaction between students and teachers, leading to a different way of managing and supervising.

On the other hand, the coordinators had kept themselves adept with technology in mind to help teachers, especially the seasoned ones, who had difficulties utilizing the educational and technological tools well. Even if they were seasoned teachers, they could still help young teachers develop their teaching pedagogy while being helped by young teachers in utilizing technology. Moreover, they expressed a need to heighten the ICT skills of teachers, especially in utilizing technology in a distance learning modality. They also made some adjustments to ensure classroom observations were done.

English Language Teachers' Teaching Processes Before and During the Pandemic

The teachers were greatly affected stakeholder by the sudden change brought about by the pandemic. However, they still saw this as challenging to work hard and perform their duty. Although the adaptation of technology made the experience more complex, the pandemic enabled them to realize that technology can be used together with traditional teaching methods and techniques. However, because of distance learning, academic learning has been stopped, and activities have become only a compliance of the subjects. This scenario resulted in students' poor performance in reading comprehension (Philippine News Agency, 2022) and other LAMC skills which were not attained due to the shift of learning modalities (DepEd USA, 2021).

It was known that the students before the pandemic went to class, listened to lectures, participated in classroom activities, and complied with the requirements asked by the teachers- teacher-student interaction was visible. However, during the pandemic, they did homeschool or distance learning modality. There were negative experiences because of this sudden alteration. Still, the situation allowed them to manage their learning using Self-learning Modules (SLMs) or online Learning Management Systems (LMS). They controlled their time and the amount of information they took in, given that technology and open learning resources on the internet had become their aid.

Nevertheless, the students' honesty and authenticity of work were in question. Many technological applications could be used to answer essays (i.e., AI). Although it was still a debate, it could be deduced that in the future, teaching-learning could be done anytime, anywhere because of technology. Learning could be acquired with a wide range of information from the *internet* due to the fast progress of technology.

Below are the teachers' experiences as they perform their job before the pandemic and during the pandemic period.

Before the pandemic, the teachers implemented various teaching strategies like pre-assessments, interactive discussions, Q and A activities, group work, and other differentiated activities. Language teachers also implement speaking activities, writing, and vocabulary building. Since the teachers can develop different English class activities, they observe the language literacy domains. These are listening, speaking, reading, writing, and viewing (K to 12 English Curriculum Guide, 2016).

During this period, teachers had the autonomy to use varied strategies. They shared that they had utilized various techniques to meet the needs of the learners. These approaches do not limit to the following: using pre-assessment before the lesson, interactive discussions, question and answer activities, group work, writing of reflection papers, differentiated activities, differentiated instruction, drills, speaking activities, vocabulary building, cooperative learning, Inquiry-based instruction, and others to teach the language and literacy domains. The teachers' resourcefulness and creativity greatly influenced students' successful teaching and learning process in delivering their lessons during this period. To support this, these were some of the statements made by the teachers:

I used these approaches- inductive learning strategy, discussion, and cooperative learning. I also believe that we should not teach grammar in isolation, so as a teacher, we should always incorporate literature in teaching grammar (Ariadne).

I am in Grade 3, so they are young. It is the peak of their curiosity, so I need to be animated and prepare colorful IMs. I incorporate gamification in the teaching of language and grammar. I use gamified lessons, songs, videos, and other apps. I tried my best to let students participate even if it is online (Demeter).

The use of gamification in teaching English gave fruitful benefits to learners. It gave learners frequent and personalized feedback, developed social learning, and increased learning motivation (Gil-Aciron, 2022). Young learners mostly enjoyed this kind of teaching technique. The teacher participants commented:

I also use gamification... it is interactive by nature; children are learning and having fun simultaneously (Artemis).

If students love what they are doing, they are more engaged (Artemis).

Videos and audio recordings develop listening and viewing competencies. They saw these resources' importance in teaching English as a second language. The teachers shared:

In listening, I played an audio story, so they listen (Demeter).

I showed them videos related to the literature and let them take down notes. I gave them guide questions to know if they understood it better.

The video reinforced the literature (Artemis).

... as my springboard, videos, and images... (Artemis).

Meanwhile, the teachers also found the interactive discussion, group discussion, and question-and-answer strategies effective in teaching speaking and listening skills. The teachers remarked:

... in every class discussion and activity, I let the students interact with me either in question-and-answer form or in a way that they will express their insights about a particular topic (Cassiopeia).

I commonly apply small group discussions (Persephone).

In developing students' reading skills, the teachers still consider the traditional ways, such as asking students to read selections and inquiring them to answer processing questions afterward. They asked students to answer them orally or to write their responses to practice their writing skills. Journal writing is an effective strategy. They said:

I always have a reading selection for students to hone their reading and comprehension skills integrated into my lesson...once a week, and I let students write journals (Ariadne).

*The literature served as a springboard. I also ask them to read ahead the assigned literary piece. The following meeting, I asked them questions... the students are given time to speak most of the time (Demeter).
I usually utilize poem and reading text as my springboard (Artemis).*

Howard Gardner developed the Multiple Intelligences Theory that significantly contributed to education. It encouraged envisioning more effective teaching methods and challenged the traditional view that there was only one kind of intelligence that a standardized test could measure (Morgan, 2021). The teachers also saw the importance of looking into the students' multiple intelligences in planning and implementing classroom activities. The teachers said the students could better understand the lesson if presented in multiple ways. By doing so, more students could be reached (Heming, 2008). The statements of the teachers supported this claim:

*If I teach literary pieces, I use strategies based on multiple intelligences. I get the data from the guidance office and group them accordingly (Artemis).
... by constantly exposing the learners with varied activities (Persephone).
I made sure that I considered the student's learning style in planning the day's lesson and the activities. I implemented differentiated activities to help the students learn these domains (Andromeda).*

Reading is also an essential skill for students. It may be considered one of the language literacies, but it plays a significant role in the student's academic achievement. It is said that learners who started reading at a young age have improved vocabulary, increased self-esteem, improved concentration and memory, enhanced creativity, and built critical thinking skills (Idulog *et al.*, 2023). In learning English, particularly in reading, the student's attitude can be affected if teachers display friendliness and helpfulness (Jambangan, 2015). Since it is an important skill, the English teachers did their best to help students acquire it. They assessed their reading comprehension level and gave remediation and intervention to students with poor reading skills. In assessing the students, the teachers in the public schools used the result of the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) program by DepEd. One teacher supported this claim:

In public schools, we have this annual Phil-IRI assessment. From the assessment result, we identified who among the learners need intervention to develop their skills in reading along with their other skills (Achilles).

Meanwhile, during the FGD, a teacher said she implemented Remedial Program in English. She was one of the teachers from the private schools who served for more than five years as an English teacher. She shared:

...we were tasked to identify students with difficulty in reading comprehension as part of our remedial program in English and reading program before the pandemic. Identifying the students is effortless since we could easily assess their reading comprehension and address these concerns (Cassiopeia).

The current standing of the Philippines in the results of PISA 2018 and World Bank 2022 showed the country's poor performance in reading comprehension. In PISA 2018, 15-year-old students are assessed for their reading literacy. They scored 340 points, with 147 differences from the average score of 487 points in OECD countries (OECD, 2018). Meanwhile, the World Bank estimated that learning poverty in the Philippines was 90.0 percent, the percentage of children aged ten (10) who cannot read or understand a simple selection (Philippine News Agency, 2022). As observed, both assessments were done before and during the pandemic. Reading comprehension has been a problem since. According to the report, many learners struggled to learn English even before the pandemic, and the sudden shift to learning from home amidst the pandemic made the struggle even harder (DepEd USA, 2021).

The next part will reveal English teachers' experiences and struggles during the pandemic.

During the Pandemic. The health crisis had given the teachers a hard time adjusting to their work's "new" nature. Most of them became instant module developers. Three teachers shared that their work was doubled and had been greatly affected by the sudden change:

Our task as a teacher was doubled... because we were asked to prepare modules for modular students and at the same time, we are preparing learning plan for our online students (Demeter).

...my task drastically changed from mainly an instructor to an all-around employee. I am saying an employee because I had to reproduce SLMs given by the Division (Persephone).

My tasks during the pandemic greatly changed. It shifted greatly. From teacher facilitator shifted to module writer and distributor (Achilles).

The pandemic has required teachers to work in new ways, adapt teaching styles, and become engaged with information and communication technologies (Mann *et al.*, 2020). However, it was apparent that they also needed help performing their language teacher duties. They also expressed the need for more authenticity in the students' work. It was called cyber-plagiarism in the study conducted by Olivia-Dumitrina *et al.*, 2019, which called for further training of teachers in tackling this issue. However, it was more prominent during the pandemic as students were exposed to the internet and AI applications. This statement made by one teacher relates to the challenges they faced during this period:

The authenticity of the students' works in their essays since there are available apps they can use (Artemis).

Since students in public schools relied on SLMs, there was non-interaction of students, which led to teachers receiving answered modules but failing to meet and evaluate the students for validation. The immediate feedback assessment technique resulted in knowledge retention and increased critical thinking (Milton & Landon, 2019). However, this did not happen due to the physical absence of the students. One of the teachers said:

... since we used purely modular method, we do not have an actual face-to-face interaction with the students, this created a great impact not only in the aspect of teaching... we shifted to guided instruction thru the use of the SLMs (Achilles).

Also, the student's reading comprehension skills were at risk during this period. Since the modality was modular, the teachers needed help to assess and follow up on how these students regarded reading skills. As one teacher manifested:

Not to discriminate or what, but since I am teaching in a public school, we cannot deny the fact that there are students who have difficulties in the four (4) macro skills, especially in the aspect of reading" (Achilles).

In the focus group discussion, another teacher also shared her struggles in implementing the reading program in the school compared to pre-pandemic.

...during a pandemic, teachers find it difficult to assess students' difficulty in comprehension, and we failed to implement the reading and remedial program in school (Cassiopeia).

The pandemic has impacted many learning opportunities, especially in-person interaction, and the modality change has obstructed learning pedagogy affecting teachers and learners (Kumar, 2021). Comparing their experiences before and during the pandemic, the teachers encountered more difficulties and challenges, especially in collaboration and interaction with students. One teacher shared:

This modality gave us limited to no interaction with our learners at all, and to be honest, this hurt the learners, especially in English language learning (Ariadne).

Moreover, the common practice of providing various activities during face-to-face classes halted due to these changes. Even private schools have limitations in terms of connectivity, and not all students have devices for online synchronous classes. Online synchronous classes have become a way to give students lectures and reminders. However, not everybody could join due to limited resources. A teacher shared:

...since some students cannot join the synchronous classes, they resort to printed materials (Demeter).

A study by Fabriz *et al.*, (2021) found that students who mostly participated in synchronous classes had experienced peer-centered activities compared to those who just relied on asynchronous activities (Fabriz *et al.*, 2021). Students who participated in the online sessions performed better than those who could not join online. The teachers shared that:

... as I compare the scores of those who join online sessions and those who were not, the students who join synchronous classes get the highest scores (Demeter).

... since many of my students are under the poverty line and had limited access to gadgets and internet, only a select few were able to achieve literacy on the language and literacy domains (Persephone).

Another obstacle was the connectivity problem which impacted students' motivation with their participation and attendance (Al-Hashmi, 2021). Many students preferred to refrain from joining online classes and relied on materials given by the teachers because of internet connectivity difficulties. Duran *et al.*, (2021) pointed out motivation as an essential factor in language learning. The presence of online classes did not solve the gap. Thus far, teachers have become creative and thought of more ways to help the students. They crafted additional instructional materials for exercise and practice, especially for those who were known to be struggling. Several teachers made manifestations:

I also give additional activities not found in the module to assess whether they have understood the lesson (Ariadne).

We provided additional activities and tasks to develop their skills further, and I always provide feedback (Achilles).

I also gave supplementary activities and catered to the student's queries sent online (Andromeda).

Additionally, the challenge was limited to learning and online classroom management. It took much work to assume that students during online sessions were listening, jotting notes, or not feeling well. It made them realize that the school environment was better than their houses. These findings supported the claims of Stamatis (2021) that the pandemic has made teachers and parents grasp that the school environment can establish a field of social learning and space for social skills acquisition. Cyberspace cannot replace it (Stamatis, 2021). The change of modality had led to disruption of social life. The students had been locked at home and could not go out due to restrictions. The pandemic has hurt the psychosocial health of learners (Li, 2022). Thus, the value formation of the learners depended on the environment to which they were exposed. In this case, at their own houses. One of the participants made this statement:

It is tough, especially in classroom discipline. When we had the online class, students could say that they have a stomach ache; during face-to-face, we know what is happening and can easily manage them (Artemis).

Since distance learning had an evident effect on students' learning, the teachers created ways to help and reach out to these learners who needed assistance. Despite the difficulties these teachers had experienced, they did not lose hope and foresee a positive future. A teacher shared that:

...during the pandemic, I was not just teaching the content; I also instill resiliency in the minds of my pupils (Artemis).

The study by Fabriz *et al.*, (2021) showed that students, especially those who join in the online synchronous modality, received more outstanding support on basic psychological needs than students who used the asynchronous mode. Noticeably, the pandemic did not only have a negative impact. Some things happened which helped not only the students

but even the teachers. A teacher further added that she became tech-savvy. Despite the constraints, they learned how to manipulate the different technological tools to perform their duty. The following remarks supported this claim:

...there are great things that happened because of the pandemic. I am now a digital native. I am very good at using various tech tools and can make learning kits weekly (Artemis).

I learned to be flexible (Demeter)

Somehow, I became proud that I could utilize technology (Ariadne).

When asked what practices they would carry out after the pandemic, they all answered that they would still utilize technology and intensify its integration inside the classroom. They shared that there should be a continuous giving of remediation materials and supplemental activities to the students. These were extension activities that reinforced the learned concepts. Furthermore, there was a learning gap, so the teachers saw them as essential. The participants made these manifestations:

The students should receive these supplementary activities since these helped facilitate learning (Andromeda).

I will continue to provide supplemental online or face-to-face activities after class discussion (Ariadne).

They also agreed that the strategies used during the pandemic still apply even in face-to-face classes. They saw the compatibility of the traditional and new mix methods for the post-pandemic period. Belias *et al.*, (2013) stated that in their study, despite the availability of traditional teaching strategies, students preferred personalized student-centered methods and recommended the said practices as accompanying tools to traditional methods. Stauffer (2022) explained the nature of “blended learning” as a strategy that uses multiple teaching methods. It is a combination of traditional classroom instruction and digital learning. Traditional instruction introduces concepts and skills, while digital learning provides additional content using technology. Several statements by the teachers relative to the applicability of the traditional and modern techniques in the classrooms are presented hereunder:

I use gamification. I still utilize these strategies, and I find it effective even in f2f classes (Artemis).

Since we made learning possible using online, I think we should not stop utilizing the apps (Demeter).

... I will carry the digitization of activities...and I think students best learn when assisted with technology during classroom instruction (Persephone).

As the world faces a precarious future, everybody must reinvent education to help address the challenges (UNESCO, 2015). Stauffer (2022) claimed to keep the traditional teaching while learning new techniques. It called for a revisit of the curriculum and the strategies used for language teaching and learning. Although there was no need to abolish the traditional approaches, it would be better not to go away from the modern methods. After all, these traditional techniques work. Moreover, the teachers’ role as facilitators of learning is still essential, though the information is available on the internet.

Supervision Styles in the Post-Pandemic Period

The instructional supervisors followed mandates and functions as autocratic and bureaucratic leaders before the pandemic. There were given rules and policies by the DepEd and private institutions to follow. The PPST, the standards of teaching LAMC, and the employee's manual were among the documents they need to refer to whenever they create decisions or assess teachers' performance. However, during the pandemic, all these were confronted. The pandemic changed the education system and their usual tasks as English coordinators (Brock *et al.*, 2021). The supervisors had no choice but to embrace more multitasking roles that were not part of their job before the pandemic. This problem was due to the need for more school personnel to facilitate logistic and clerical work, from printing SLMs to distribution and retrieval. They juggle several duties with their two hands, testing their flexibility and adaptability.

Meanwhile, technology had taken its toll when supervision tasks were seen to be a bit easier with its presence. "Virtual supervision" (Cano & Garcia, 2013) became a part of the supervisory activity where they can access anytime, anywhere using gadgets and an internet connection. Laissez-faire and democratic supervision were also seen to be effective during this period. They also take on the essential role of the teachers in helping to succeed in each endeavor of learning and to work with them as a team in creating decisions.

Below are the experiences of the English supervisors as they work on the transition from the pandemic to the post-pandemic period.

Brock *et al.*, (2021) posited that instructional coordinators are challenged while working with teachers in the virtual classroom. This setup was primarily new, so problem-solving became essential as they worked with teachers to deliver online classes (Brock *et al.*, 2021). The coordinators also recognized all the challenges faced brought by the pandemic and the changes it had posted to the education system and their tasks. Hence, they continued to remain resilient and robust.

The coordinators shared how they became flexible and adaptable due to the sudden changes they encountered; they were also exposed to multitasking activities that challenged them to be agile. Their real-life and practical training taught them to shift their mindset and improve their leadership approaches (Korhani, 2021).

"As a supervisor, I have to ensure that despite many obstacles during the pandemic, the learners' learning should not be affected" (Hermes).

"The pandemic challenged me to perform better as an English Coordinator"
(Athena).

"Coordinators should be ahead of the game and flexible" (Athena).

The additional tasks included making sure that the teachers were ready, distributed the modules, executed their teaching tasks appropriately, and that problems, as they occurred, were handled well, were just some of the things they juggled with their two hands. Moreover, they became logistics officers. They do not just enter the online class

to observe classes but also ensure that the students who chose SLMs received and returned the learning materials and that the contents of the Learning Management System (LMS) are up to date and correct. They relayed that it was not just to ensure that problems in schools would not arise, but also, they had to support the teachers as much as they could. The statements of coordinators supported this claim:

I needed to familiarize myself with the learning management system our school was using... for me to be a good example for my colleagues or to be a model in the online classes (Hermes).

... There is the additional task of printing, counting, delivering, and collecting the modules. I oversee these things aside from my original job; we tried our best to distribute and retrieve these modules on time (Ares).

I oriented the teachers on the changes and provided them with technical assistance for an easier transition (Helen).

Prihatin *et al.*, (2021) claimed that the teachers' performance depended on the supervision of academic leaders. If the coordinators perform well, the teachers will also do the same. It was further reiterated that academic supervision should promote awareness among the teachers and provide them with encouragement and motivation to improve their performance (Prihatin *et al.*, 2021). Another change in this period was the need to intensify communication so the teacher would adequately perform their tasks. Two teacher participants mentioned:

It has to be constant communication and monitoring of the teachers in all aspects...Without it, no matter how the teachers work well, absence of monitoring, nobody will validate it, and he will assume that he is doing great (Zeus).

Every day, I talk to different teachers, then weekly I talk to a teacher about his/her progress (Hermes).

These experiences made them flexible and agile leaders. It had been evident in the accounts of the English coordinators. The situation made them realize that technology had a significant role in education and supervision. Furthermore, they also realized they had to participate in this revolution. In addition, since technology is the trend, there is a need to improve internet connectivity across schools and rural areas. Teachers and learners should also accept these changes to succeed in supervision innovation (Mhishi & Gwizangwe, 2022). The coordinators revealed:

Technology should still be used even in post-pandemic, a mix of both (Hermes).

The use of technology took its big role in the change that we will see because of the pandemic (Ares).

Amidst the modality change, they had seen more work to do. Among them was the readiness of teachers and students to adapt to the changes brought about by the pandemic, especially in the education sector. Istiningsih and Widodo (2020) highlighted teachers' readiness in their research. *First* was the arrangement of the supervisory program, which included the supervision instruments emphasizing the use of digital

media; the *second* was the utilization of various and attractive digital media, which allowed students to become more active and creative; and *third*, the teachers' training and education program to increase their literacy in ICT. They expressed that while maintaining the practices before, highlighting technology. The situation awakened the education system to embrace technology as part of instruction and supervision, the highlight of the pandemic. They had also agreed that the pre-pandemic and pandemic modes of supervision could be carried out and combined during the post-pandemic. It underlined retaining the practices and learning materials used before and during the pandemic and combining them with educational technology in the post-pandemic (Istiningsih & Widodo, 2020). The coordinators mentioned these in their statements:

I think there will be a need to combine the pre-pandemic and pandemic criteria (Athena).

... the same with the practices we did before the pandemic and retain the materials used during the pandemic. Like the use of technology. It should still be used even post-pandemic. A mix of both (Hermes).

With the proliferation of technology and its influence on educational processes, I think it must include observation and other monitoring tools" (Perseus).

Also, this period intensified the use of technology. It played a vital role in the delivery of instruction and supervision. It had become a tool for communication, monitoring, and observation. Coordinators also utilized it to coach, mentor, and give feedback to teachers under their care. Technology is an effective tool for supervision, but it still needs to be extensively used (Wiyono *et al.*, 2021). In addition, the coordinators needed to enrich the use of ICT in implementing instructional supervision for more effective and quality teaching-learning processes and outcomes.

In the intervening time, the coordinators saw how easier it is to work with paper works and facilitate online submissions. They also saw it as a convenient tool to validate the works of their teachers and give immediate feedback, even in a distance modality. Thus, they proposed that technology will still be utilized for supervision and teaching in implementing face-to-face classes. The coordinators manifested this:

Intensifying on integrating ICT in both aspects, supervision, and class observations (Ares).

I have to adapt the modernization plan... for the schools to progress and to integrate the ICT to the teaching-learning process (Ares).

Likewise, the adaptability, openness, and flexibility of differentiated and inclusivity of education were also some of the significant changes observed in this period. Inclusive education in the Philippines, as defined in DepEd Order No. 21, s., 2019, was said to be the core of the K to 12 basic Education Program. It promoted the right of every Filipino learner to equitable, culture-based, quality, and complete primary education regardless of sex, disability, ability, age, social class, culture, religion, and others (DO No. 21, s., 2019).

As observed, the pandemic has made all schools accept students. ...*inclusive education could be applied post-pandemic* (Perseus). Even private schools waived the entrance examinations or placement tests. By admitting these students, it had become the responsibility of the schools to cater to them without prejudice. Moreover, it is the responsibility of the schools to provide for the student's needs until they finish primary education. To perform this, there is a need to retool the teachers through professional development and training that focuses on addressing the needs of diverse learners. The statements of the coordinators supported it:

Retooling and upskilling teachers teaching skills to address learners' needs (Ares).
... to refresh teachers with the English curriculum implementation during learning action cells (Perseus).

Finally, the coordinators also recognized the vital roles of the teachers in planning and decision-making. Since they journeyed together, these teachers have experienced firsthand and can give many ideas on developing and improving policies. If the teachers offered more direct input, an innovative and sustainable educational policy would be achieved. Furthermore, without their involvement would often result in ill-conceived and nearly impossible policies (Watkins, 2022). The coordinators also shared that they must collaborate with teachers and other stakeholders. One coordinator said:

Teachers can also tell which is better or doable. I am very open to hearing their suggestions since I know I am not the most knowledgeable in the group (Athena).

Since these teachers had witnessed how the students were and what their struggles were, they should be the ones to design intervention programs or extension tasks to meet the curriculum standards (Brock *et al.*, 2021). The statements of the coordinators support this claim:

It is more of facilitating and getting ideas from the different teachers. Everyone in the team must be involved (Zeus).
I am very open to hearing their suggestions since I know I am not the most knowledgeable in the group...I am not only evaluating but also learning strategies from them (Athena).
I also need to learn their teaching ... (Helen).

To sum up, the situation called on the flexibility and adaptability of the coordinators in preparing themselves for the transition from pandemic to post-pandemic. They shared the adjustments and strategies to cope with the situation's demands. Multitasking activities and the different modes of communication were used in optimum.

Moreover, they had agreed that integrating pre-pandemic and post-pandemic activities helped improve the supervision activities. They saw how vital the intensification of the usage of technological tools is in delivering instruction and supervision. It considered the value of openness, adaptability, and inclusivity in education during the COVID-19 crisis. Thus, they recognized the vital roles of teachers in planning and creating decisions for

the betterment of the supervision and teaching strategies during the post-pandemic. Effective and outstanding teaching and learning rely on teachers' leadership skills and contributions (Warren, 2021).

Teaching and Learning Processes in the Post-Pandemic Period

The teachers and students experienced firsthand the impact of the change. It has become a topsy-turvy ride for both as they adapt technology to their daily tasks as teachers and learners. However, the teacher's adaptability and flexibility helped them see the "hope" that teaching and learning will not stop despite the apprehensions. The limited support for learners at home and their lack of training in doing online classes, the technical problems they encountered as they prepared materials, and the different work demands challenged them to upskill themselves to be ready for the brutal battle. Technology was there to help.

Nevertheless, the teachers were still optimistic about the future of education. They expressed their readiness to embrace technology as part of the tools to help them realize their tasks as a teacher. Below are the teachers' manifestations as they describe their teaching and learning experiences during the transition from the pandemic to the post-pandemic period.

The teachers and students were most affected by the education modality change. There was an alteration in their tasks and routines to attune to the different work demands. The teachers experienced disadvantages in technical problems, limited support and resources for learners at home, and a lack of training in conducting online classes (Nikolopoulou, 2022). Nevertheless, there were also positive experiences like the learners' familiarization with technology. Because of the situation, they had to embrace the distance learning modality. They also learned to use technology and became acquainted with the different educational applications used in online classes. The teachers' narrations supported this claim:

Learning did not stop, and we contacted our students differently. Somehow, I became proud of myself that I could utilize technology. I can do PowerPoint presentations and place them inside the google classroom. I have learned how to make google classroom (Ariadne). My skills in using the apps for teaching and learning, like Canva and others, had improved (Artemis). All performances were recorded and sent via online platforms like Facebook Messenger or Gmail (Persephone). I saw the advantage of the pandemic for the teachers; I learned to manipulate technological gadgets (Demeter).

Because of the unconventionality, the teachers saw the need to upgrade themselves and prepare physically, mentally, intellectually, and professionally during the transition. They saw the importance of holistically preparing themselves to adapt to the trends and the demands of the situation. It was also essential to maintain good teaching practices and not reduce the standard of learning activities even with the modality shift. It will attract

learners' interest and engagement in the activities designed by the teachers (Nikolopoulou, 2022). Below are some of the teachers' manifestations on how they will deal with the transitions as they prepare for the face-to-face classes:

... I will study the curriculum maps again. Although we make learning plans, I need to review my previous curriculum maps to plot the topics (Artemis).

I equip myself by undergoing a series of training and seminars focusing on the teaching strategies that can be used post-pandemic (Persephone).

I should be flexible with such adjustments and be back on track by preparing the necessary instructional materials (Cassiopeia).

I am crafting the needed lesson logs for the face-to-face teaching (Achilles).

The teachers also saw how important to consider the students' safety when face-to-face classes resume. Since the minimum health protocols are still in place, the teachers see themselves as a guide to ensure the virus is contained. The effects of the pandemic would take many years. It is essential to recognize that the community could bounce back and ensure equity in education for all students (DepEd USA, 2021). The teachers' primary duty is to ensure the safety of the students under their watch. This time, they had to ensure that the learners followed the policies and the minimum health protocols required and that learning should happen inside the classroom. The teachers shared:

I am in school not just to teach but also to ensure the learners' safety... they understand the problem we are facing right now. Just that we have to be consistent and give constant reminders (Demeter).

Since there is a two-year gap, these students need to review or refresh their skills, especially in English grammar, spelling, and communication activities (Andromeda).

The teachers also admitted how the situation affected their mental health. According to them, regular meetings and conversations help keep emotional and social support at work. It coincided with the coordinators' claim that communication is a significant factor in keeping the teachers on track. Kush *et al.*, (2022) reported that the teachers' mental health during the COVID-19 pandemic had a greater prevalence of anxiety symptoms and higher levels of distress than when they taught in-person classes. However, the DepEd recognized the personnel's mental health and well-being and launched a series of sessions for Mental Health and Psychosocial Support Services (MHPSS). The program gave lessons and tips on handling different emotions and feelings due to the pandemic. It followed the World Health Organization's claim that there is no health without mental health (DepEd, 2020). Even with uncertainties, the teachers claimed they needed to be ready for every change. In support, the teacher participants narrated:

The teachers also got stressed about the situation. There were symposiums about handling changes or transitions (Artemis).

I am preparing my mental and physical health. The pandemic caused several changes in the mental and physical health of the teachers; slow

*adjustments are necessary so that we would not experience any negative effects on our body (Achilles).
I guess I have to be ready since I know that we will prepare the classroom ... I am not yet sure what the process is, but yes, I need to be ready (Demeter).*

With the implementation of the complete face-to-face learning modality in the post-pandemic period, teachers needed more self-preparation to adapt to integrating learning technologies in face-to-face settings. Aside from that, the opening of face-to-face classes prompted teachers to spend their own money to prepare the classrooms (Tagare, 2023). It commonly happens in public schools since they need more funds to support their needs as they comply with public health standards. Moreover, the two-year homeschooling made students get used to controlling their time. The long-distance education caused some students to disobey since discipline and values were not observed (Tagare, 2023). Nevertheless, the teachers still see these challenges and are ready to transition from distance to face-to-face classes. The teachers narrated:

*I have my old and new teaching strategies so that my students do not find it hard to adapt to the academic transition” (Cassiopeia).
I equip myself by undergoing a series of training and seminars which focus on the teaching strategies that can be used post-pandemic (Persephone).
I prepared new strategies knowing that teaching students in this post-pandemic period will be quite difficult than usual (Andromeda).
I also attended seminars to prepare myself for the new normal” (Ariadne).
I am also preparing the materials that will be needed, especially during this post-pandemic. We must develop our skills now because, again, change is constant (Achilles).*

To sum up, the teachers helped themselves to be equipped with technological skills to adapt to the changes in the teaching system from pandemic to post-pandemic. During the post-pandemic, the teachers saw how technology would become a norm in education. However, most significantly, they should be prepared to integrate technology into the different teaching approaches to address the learners’ needs. They also saw how mental and intellectual preparedness was needed to show their adaptability and flexibility to the new system.

The English supervisors’ values and beliefs to help recreate the future

When asked what keeps the coordinators going when facing the changes and challenges, especially during the pandemic, they agreed that they felt responsible for their teachers and the learners. They believed that the teachers would perform their duty correctly with proper supervision. The higher the effectiveness of the academic leader, the better the teachers’ performance. Furthermore, to intensify the teachers’ ability to teach, guidance and direction from the supervisor are needed (Hakim *et al.*, 2021). It envisions that the coordinators believed in quality performance, and quality learning during post-pandemic. They inspire have a progressive mindset and become open-minded to adapt to the

changing system. They expressed their passion and love in serving and promoting good relationships and achieving eminent outputs and learnings for supervisors, teachers, and the students under their care.

When teachers perform well, students will also receive quality teaching-learning experiences. The coordinators in these narrations manifest this claim:

... looking at the welfare of my teachers and, simultaneously, the students are what keeps me going (Ares).

I would also want the teachers in my time to be as effective as they can be (Athena).

I always remember that when I have the best teachers in the department, they could also have the best students (Perseus).

So that these students can get the quality education they deserve (Hermes)

The fulfillment and happiness of seeing my students grow and learn simultaneously, the feeling of contentment in sharing my knowledge with my fellow teachers (Helen).

In the study entitled “*Pandemic school leadership: Lessons learned and implications for post-COVID schooling*” by Rochon (2021), a participant claimed that observations and experiences, critical analysis, and reflections shaped his teaching philosophy and practice. The coordinators gained new experiences because of the pandemic; this harnessed their practices as leaders and teachers.

In this study, the coordinators expressed that they had a responsibility toward the teachers and students, which was evident in some of the statements made:

I am responsible for what they will become. If they have not learned, it is my fault (Athena).

The learners deserve the best from teachers. This fuels me to continue providing technical assistance to my fellow teachers (Perseus).

I wanted to do my best in my work and to influence my co-educators to improve their selves ... making them an effective teacher (Ares).

... great passion and compassion are the values that I want to instill in the hearts and minds of my English teachers for them to perform well and be reminded of their profession as educators of the young (Hermes).

... as a teacher and supervisor, I never rely on the “bahala na” ideology. I must be prepared all the time, especially in dealing with my students, and for any uncertainty of the future (Athena).

These beliefs were their principles and values, which had driven them to go the extra mile to serve and perform their duties, thinking of both welfare of the teachers under their care and the students. The participants also believed in *progressivism*, at the same time, wanted to impose the same mindset on the teachers. “Progressive education” in the 21st century was a phrase that helped maintain the liberation of traditional pedagogies (Lee & Tippett, 2019). To add, Allen (2020), in her article entitled “*Viewing leadership through a systems lens (in a time of pandemic)*,” said that the result of the pandemic had made an

accelerating impact on every leader's actions. The message was clear that education should be moving towards modernization while maintaining the traditional standards based on the actual experiences of the coordinators. This claim is echoed in the coordinator's narrations:

It is my progressive mindset. When the need arises like a need to adjust, to achieve progress, everyone should take part to realize the target (Zeus).

If only we are progressivist in dealing with all that matters in the educative world, then supervision could be realistic and advanced (Ares).

I just follow the constructivist and progressivist belief (Ares).

I envision a progressive working environment (Helen).

The FGD highlighted the coordinators' continuous desire to provide quality instruction with technology integration. They mentioned that open-mindedness in learning, embracing technology, and imbibing 21st-century skills became essential tools to embrace the future as technology integration improved student performance (Boholano *et al.*, 2021). In addition, the teachers' productivity and ability to use technology capacitated and prepared the 21st-century learners for the Fourth Industrial Revolution (Boholano *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, the coordinators accepted the changes in education, and that technology played a vital role. The coordinators mentioned these in their statements:

Open-mindedness and a learned individual. I foresee myself as a better person, filled with wisdom and ideas that I can share with everyone, especially with my teachers (Helen).

... it is but natural that we embrace changes in education and play our roles well as we transition to a better future (Perseus).

I want to strengthen the use of technology. We also must enhance and help teachers who are not into it (Athena).

... not to be isolated from the traditional delivery of the lesson. If we teach the 21st-century skills, they must also acquire and teach the 21st-century skills (Ares).

The coordinators also wanted to embrace technology, specifically in supervision. They said they became more efficient in performing the task since they could work on paper works, for instance, anywhere, as long as there is a computer and reliable internet connection. Moreover, instructional supervision is conducted using technologies (Boholano *et al.*, 2021). These technologies are in communication media such as Facebook, Twitter, Google, Pinterest, and Instagram. Besides, web-based tools increased the collaboration between the coordinators and the teachers (Wiyono *et al.*, 2021). As the coordinators stated:

... if we allow ICT modernization in supervision (Ares).

English supervision would be adopting face-to-face and online observation. It would also look into the integration of technology and the ways of addressing students' learning styles and intelligence (Perseus).

It is no longer possible to return to what was done before (Athena).

...this time, the supervisors should include the use of technology... Technology can get the students' attention, of course, with the teacher's creativity (Hermes)
... technology is strengthened for all, not only for ICT teachers. Adapting to the needs of the time (Athena).
...it would become less stressful to teachers, paperless for us supervisors" (Perseus).

The pandemic has provoked them to where they can go and what they can do as academic leaders. Their “*hope*” was connected to the future, and the *future* was nothing without hope (Hogan & Bruce, 2013). With constant communication and open lines, the *hopes* of the educators and supervisors will become their willpower to continue striving for what is best for the learners. Moreover, they see it as a weapon to update one another on recent trends and ensure that these practices will help them deliver quality instruction. The coordinators shared:

Many talks will be needed (Athena).
Collaboration is also important (Helen).
We meet and coordinate (Zeus).

The absolute passion and love for teaching is the future primary goal of the coordinators. As said, they held themselves responsible for the teachers' and students' success. The coordinator's self-efficacy can play a moderating role, an intrinsic motivation, and a created self-efficacy in the supervisee (Su *et al.*, 2022). Furthermore, their task is to make teachers maintain their professionalism. If supervision is applied regularly, it will impact the student's learning and achievement since the teachers are the main instrument in producing high-achieving students (Yulianti, 2021). They also believed that successful supervision, teaching, and learning work wonders. Some of their future projections also include seeing themselves as mediators and facilitators. As one coordinator mentioned:

As a supervisor, I see myself as the mediator and facilitator (Zeus).

The coordinators also believed that to help teachers, they must be full models of integrating technology in the classrooms. They should work hard for the teachers and students, as pointed out by two of the coordinator respondents:

Coordinators should also be advanced. More advance from the teachers. Supervisors should be ahead of the game (Athena).
... a leader must perform because of the impact of the pandemic (Helen).

Meanwhile, they admit that their task was not only focused on the teacher alone but on the students as well. One coordinator supported this claim in this wise:

...not only the teacher is the focus of the observation but will also include the students. Technology can get the students' attention, of course, with the teacher's creativity (Hermes).

They aimed to provide both teachers and students with better ways of doing things that are products of their experience, another future projection of a coordinator:

... as an educational leader, I could extend both teachers' and students' limits to another level by providing them with better ways of doing things that are products of experience and research (Perseus).

To sum up, the English coordinators' beliefs and how these helped them recreate their ideal future were already in their minds and were part of their plans as they faced the future. The coordinators claimed that teachers and students were their responsibility. They felt responsible for their success and even failures. They believed that when they perform good supervision, the teachers will teach well, and it will affect how the students will learn. They are responsible for the teacher's and student's success and learning. However, without open-mindedness, collaboration, and open communication, success will not happen. According to Geary (2020), communication gave joy and efficiency to the supervisors and teachers while they maintained a heightened level of care for one another. In the future, they still believed that *passion and love* of teaching should be the primary values of all educators to continue helping learners.

Worldview

The teachers see themselves as responsible "*in place of parents*" or *loco parentis* to the students. They believed in the essential roles they play in helping learners achieve their dreams and aspirations in life. They expressed their commitment and love towards their job and the students and aspired to be a good influence. They also hope to give them better education and see them globally competitive with the English language as their tool to succeed. In the broader scope, the teachers see themselves as a responsible individual who can help produce global citizens. They did not lose hope that there was a great future ahead for the learners.

Below were the teachers' manifestations of how they see themselves as teachers and what values and beliefs helped them reimagine ideal futures for English language teaching and learning.

These beliefs, practices, and attitudes were significant in understanding and refining educational progressions (OECD [Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development], 2009). In the constructivist view, students were not passive learners but active participants in teaching and learning. Teachers who believed in this view effectively facilitated students' inquiry skills, problem-solving skills, and active participation in instructional activities (OECD, 2009). Moreover, the teachers' "*quality*" determined the gains in student achievement (Guerriero, 2014). The teachers who participated in this study were optimistic for the future. They expressed their love of their work and their students. Love and passion fueled them to continue their job despite their challenges during the pandemic. Further, a new social contract for education was needed to allow them to think differently about teaching and learning and the connection between

learners, information, and the world (UNESCO [United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization], 2015).

Presented with challenging roles and new tasks to meet the needs of the learners and, at the same time, following the policies given by the DepEd, the teachers were asked what kept them doing their job. These were the statements made by some of them:

I love my job. That is the only principle I have now as a teacher (Demeter).

My passion for teaching and molding the students into becoming efficient citizens in the community (Andromeda).

... no money can be equivalent to the student's learning" (Achilles).

That inspires me to do more and be more for them. I want to be a teacher that has an impact. A teacher that influences them to be the best version of themselves (Ariadne).

The teachers had also seen the importance of their role in the lives of their students. They believed that by doing their best, they could help learners achieve their goals in life, and seeing them succeed was also their achievement. The teachers' roles towards students affected the achievement and motivation of the learners. These roles will depend on the situation. Sadiq (2020), in her study entitled "*The impact of the teacher's role on students' achievement and motivation in ESP teaching,*" stated that the teacher could encourage and motivate learners for students to reach better learning in English for Specific Purposes (ESP).

Teacher excellence matters to students' achievement (Sirait, 2016). They manifested that their roles to the students were more than just a lecturer, following the term "*loco parentis,*" which meant "*in place of a parent,*" which applied to all teachers toward their students (Mohammed, 2014). Some of the teachers attested to this:

I believe this serves as my extended family that I need to be responsible for and make sure they did not just enter to learn (Cassiopeia).

... our job is to give the learners the education they deserve no matter what the change and trials may come both in the education system and our personal lives as teachers (Achilles).

I believe that we teachers need to help our students and future generations to become better individuals (Persephone).

... it is my utmost happiness to see my students learn something from me (Ariadne).

It was also evident that even if they saw and experienced the problems during the transition firsthand, they were hopeful for the future. This future gave them "hope" to envision successful teaching and learning, especially in English. Moreover, the teachers interviewed wanted to share the success of the education system and the students. The following statements supported their hopes:

I hope to see globally competitive individuals as a product of successful English language teaching (Andromeda).

I hope English and the learning process are more in tuned with what is in the grassroots (Persephone).

I am hoping that there will be a low rate of readers with no comprehension and that students will master the basic rules of grammar (Ariadne).

I hope someday there will be no more learners who will have this kind of struggle because this will greatly impact their learning and future (Artemis).

They were also optimistic about the success of the country. They expressed how they look forward to the betterment of the nation, which was why they work hard for the learners. They always take everything positively, especially the technology integration into teaching and learning the English language. Adequately harnessing technology integration into teaching ensures effective teaching-learning (Nikade, 2022). Moreover, they also anticipate seeing their students take the lead and become responsible citizens. The teachers' statements supported it:

I can see that there will be a great future for English language teaching. It is because the English language has now come to the point that it became like a necessity, especially for workers abroad or internationally (Achilles).

... soon, the Philippines will be a major English-speaking country that can produce proficient and well-equipped teachers that can compete globally (Ariadne).

I also firmly believe that effort produces achievement (Achilles).

I believe that we teachers need to help our students and future generations to become better individuals (Persephone).

To sum up, the teachers simultaneously expressed love and passion towards their work and students. This love kept them going, seeing hope for the nation. They saw themselves as responsible for the learners' futures and their capacity to create a good one for these students. They are optimistic about the country's global scenario with English proficiency and have projected that they could produce globally competitive individuals through their passion and love. They believed that they will serve as the *light* of students' paths. Thus, the bright future for students and the English teaching-learning process is *in their hands*.

Metaphors. Metaphors were popular with researchers to explain phenomena that included change. However, these metaphors can only help represent the continuous and shifting of progression (Rogerson, 2021). The metaphors are the unconscious awareness of deep stories as bases of sense or logic (Inayatullah *et al.*, 2016), a representation, identity or dissertation (Bussey, 2008).

The following sections presented the derived metaphors of English coordinators and teachers that support future supervision and teaching as they face the post-pandemic period. The metaphors were arranged where the most prominent or preferred lived futures

were seen in the first part then followed by the rest, these signify the supervisors' and teachers' ideal futures.

Metaphors Developed to Support the English Language's Future Supervision

Metaphors are deep stories and emotive dimensions. This level provides an emotional experience. At this level, it is said "*We do not make predictions but give alternatives to shape the future*" (Inayatullah, 2017). It is also far more explicit and subjective compared to the other levels. Moreover, narratives give power and effect to all CLA levels (Milojevic & Inayatullah, 2015).

This section presents the English coordinators' metaphors as to how they see the future of supervision in English teaching. The associated meaning and the significant statements from the interviews also supported the myth or metaphors of the coordinators. It will be followed by a narrative of the most preferred future of English language coordinators- ***an exam, a test***.

An exam, a test. Supervision is associated with the policies and procedures to follow when taking an exam, or when the results came in, there is a need to do something with the outcome based on the standards. It came from the statement, "*I can compare it to an exam or test, which is a procedure to establish the quality and performance of one's knowledge.*" It established that supervision was like an exam with ratings based on the standards. The manner of evaluation will be more straightforward because of the ideals.

A laptop. Supervision is associated with an upgraded supervisor. It came from the statement: "*I see myself as a device, probably a laptop. Like laptops, coordinators need to be upgraded for technological skills to adapt to modernization. A laptop has specifications and brand; an upgrading is done regularly to stay attune to the demand of the market.*"

A bird. Supervision is associated with an animal flying high like a bird. This statement explained it further: "*English language supervision is something like going up because of the fast-changing approaches, strategies, and standards, to meet the demands of society.*" The changes demanded creativity, and the coordinators played an essential role in overseeing and solving problems.

A mobile phone. Supervision is associated with supervisors having appropriate specifications and having the capacity to supervise. It was explained further by the statement: "*It keeps upgrading itself with added features*". The coordinator's skills need to be adaptable, open, and flexible to changes, like a phone which always needs upgrading to cater to society's needs.

The internet. Supervision is associated with a responsive, dynamic, and active leader. It was explained through the statement: "*It is evolving, dynamic, and integrating because from time-to-time supervision changes to suit the primary needs of the clients.*" The coordinators had to be flexible and adaptable to changes brought about by the pandemic.

When asked to suggest more metaphors that describe supervision in the future, the participants gave the following: (a) *a blueprint for a building*, (b) *a correctional eyeglass* to see the reality, and (c) *an oil lamp* to light the path as they journey to the new normal. These ranked metaphors came from the coordinators' interviews.

Alternative Future #1: *An exam, a test, the metaphor for instructional supervision.* Instructional supervision is associated with the policies and procedures to follow when assessment results are utilized; gaps can be identified and addressed through its results. It came from the statement, *"I can compare it to an exam or test, which is a procedure to establish the quality and performance of one's knowledge."* It established that supervision was like an exam with ratings based on the standards. The manner of evaluation will be more straightforward due to the ideals.

Because of the changes that happened due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the English supervisors observed many changes, especially in the performance of their tasks. They used traditional observation forms and collected and checked printed lesson plans, test questions, and curriculum maps. They follow protocols based on the mandates of the DepEd or the policies and regulations for private institutions. They can quickly call teachers' attention, see personally what happens inside the classroom, give teachers feedback, give reminders and check on their teaching performance. However, when the shift of modality happened, there were usual supervisory tasks that were, if not difficult, impossible to perform due to the lack of interaction. Some activities, like class observations, were done out of compliance and not to check whether the teaching-learning process had accomplished its intended goals. With this, it is a call for the authorities always to include regular evaluations/ tests to check whether the current practices are still applicable in this fast turn of events (Khaef & Karimnia, 2021).

Deepening: Examinations/tests. These educational measurements facilitate formative, summative, or even diagnostic evaluations (Kolanchery, 2015). If put in the context of supervision, test or exam results can be used to assess the effectiveness of existing mandates and policies being issued by the Department of Education and private institutions. It is to find out what suits best and what not. It is to align supervisory practices to the current set-up. Thus, having the process of evaluation help in the planning process to describe whether supervisory programs being implemented still operate and if these can still be carried out to achieve successful instructional supervision (Bailey, 2006).

Figure 4, shows the "futures" of English Supervision grounded on the metaphors given by the respondents. In this portion, the researcher co-creates the future of supervision in a form of illustrations for creative visualization to develop a vision (Inayatullah, 2013) in the duration of five and 10 years. It aims to help decision makers shift their mindset, meeting where they are and where they can go using the change progression approach (Inayatullah, 2013).

Figure 4 The futures of English supervision.

Since the ideal future involves standards and changes due to evaluation and assessments, the English supervision can also be seen as a *first-aid tool* to amend the reparations caused by the impact of the pandemic in the educational system for the next few years. This involves the diagnosis of policies to see much broader aspects for upgrade or rehabilitation, as they look for medications that can cure all mishaps and address challenges with appropriate skills and dynamic leadership (Villegas & Garcia, 2022). Computer or technology had given much help in the performance of the supervisors during the pandemic. Thus, the adaption of ICT (Singh *et al.*,2021) in the supervision leads to an ideal vision of using artificial intelligence to aid English supervisors or coordinators into more advanced directives in supervising teachers in the teaching and learning process.

Metaphors Developed to Support the English Language’s Future in Teaching and Learning Process

This portion presents the English teachers conceived teaching-learning practices. During the FGD, the teachers ranked the metaphors from their interviews. These were presented with the associated meanings and the significant statements from their answers. These metaphors were ranked based on their most preferred “lived future.” It is followed by a narrative about the most preferred future of teachers in terms of English teaching and learning- **a globe**.

A globe. Teaching is associated with making learners use English globally. The statement elaborated: “*I am an English teacher; I can communicate with people around the globe.*” In addition, learning the English language will help learners connect worldwide.

A seedling. Teaching is associated with caring and meeting the learners’ needs. It was explained by the statement: “*...a seedling grows and improves when given the proper*

care and the needed nutrients to sustain its life and growth. This is true with English language teaching; it evolves and improves as time passes by, with the help of effective and efficient educators in the field.” Moreover, an influential English teacher works hard to sustain and help learners grow.

A pen. Teaching is associated with engraving knowledge and skills in the learners’ minds. It was explained in the statement: *“It symbolizes knowledge because you can write anything you know. As a teacher, it is my role to impart knowledge. Without the pen, we cannot function as a teacher or function as a student.”* Further, the learners inscribed and retained the lessons to be used in real-life situations.

A plane. Teaching is associated with regular checking and maintenance. As it was said: *“...which has reached the sky and now soaring high but still needs to land to check for problems and maintenance.”* A learner cannot fly high like a plane when the wings and engines (English) are not checked and fixed.

A glass. Teaching is associated with frail and fragile learners. This is explained in this statement: *“It will depend on who handles the glass. If you are not careful, it might break. The future of English teaching will depend on the teacher handling it. If the teacher herself is slacking, students will not learn. Coordinators as well, if they do not know how to handle the teachers, they will also break like glass.”* English teachers must deliver the lesson effectively. Given that learners are human and have emotions, it will also be the same with the teachers. The coordinators should also handle the teachers well.

A business. Teaching is associated with industrialization. This statement finds support with this narration: *“English is used worldwide. The English language is not for conversational purposes anymore, but it is now widely used in business and other professions.”* If there is a demand for skill in language use, teaching it should also need to flourish.

A clock/time. Teaching is associated with time and effort. The statement: *“It also reminds us that time is a limited resource, so we should use it wisely and productively,”* is a matter of fact. Due to the fast-changing environment, teachers must be resourceful and use instructional time productively.

When asked to suggest more metaphors that describe English teaching in the future, the participants gave the following: (a) *a key* that opens opportunities, (b) *an outdated operating system (OS)* of a phone that needs an upgrade, (c) *a rubber band*, elastic, flexible, and can bounce back, (d) *a plant* to be taken care of, given attention and be loved, (e) *a gavel* to call the attention and to put an order, and (f) *a pencil* to draw one’s future.

Alternative Future # 2: *A globe. An English teaching and learning metaphor.* Teaching is associated with making learners use English globally. The statement elaborated: *“I am an English teacher; I can communicate with people around the globe.”* In addition, learning the English language will help learners connect worldwide. This supports the

claims of Ngole & Mkulu, (2021), Ayandoja *et al.*, (2017), Oguta *et al.*, (2019), and Kipruto, (2009), that teachers' efficiency can affect students' performance, effective English teachers can harness the learners' communication skills, thus making them globally competitive individuals.

"*English rules*" is a line suggesting the universality of the language (Crystal, 2003). Needless to say, English is a lingua franca, which most native and non-native speakers use for business communication (Rao, 2019), including Filipinos. The English teachers saw the importance of teaching the subject so learners could communicate with people worldwide. With the advent of advanced technology, the world has become smaller as people can connect using different social media platforms. It has become evident when the pandemic struck. Because of lockdowns and the closure of physical schools, *virtual schools* opened. Online classes and distance learning were done worldwide, allowing schools to accept international students. However, Karkar-Esperat (2018) claimed that international students' proficiency in the English language was essential for success and satisfaction in an online class.

Deepening: A globe. A miniature form of the earth - an earth where people live ideally in harmony and unity. It can also be related to globalization, that stated all people would become citizens of a *global village*. Moreover, due to the rise of information technology, interconnectedness, and a unified world can be possible (Meurs *et al.*, 2011). In this study, teaching and learning English was compared to a globe, the living planet, recognizing English as the language that fixes barriers, a learned language by many, a tool in building businesses, building relationships, and promoting peace and harmony. English as a second language cannot be learned if the English teachers will not find appropriate teaching strategies and techniques suitable to the needs of the learners. Since English is the communication medium worldwide, teachers must ensure that the imparted knowledge and skills are practiced in school and real-life situations. These teachers need the efficacy and skills to do these tasks efficiently.

Moreover, teaching English is a task that requires time and effort (Kwee, 2022). A teacher should be resilient, creative, and resourceful (Suarez, 2022). Thus, English teaching should open opportunities, upgrade the learners' skills and talents, make learners flexible, give consideration and order (Satharatthana, 2021), help *draw* one's future, and show love and care to mold young people.

Figure 5 shows the futures of English teaching and learning. In this portion, the researcher co-creates the future of English teaching and learning in a form of illustrations for artistic picturing to develop an image (Inayatullah, 2013) in the duration of five and 10 years. The results are constructed with the support of the metaphors provided by the teacher participants.

Figure 5

The futures of English teaching and learning.

English is a global language, used for communication and to promote globalization. The English teachers has described their ideal future with a metaphor of a globe. They see the importance of their role in producing globally competitive individual and assumed the responsibility of also becoming one. Teaching through gamification came out from the narratives of the participants. This has led the researcher to foresee English teaching as a game in the concept of *a roblox*, an online game platform and a game creation system that allow players to plug-in tournaments or enjoy ready-made events. This context is the same with how the teachers manipulate technology in the classroom, frontal or virtual set-up (Stauffer, 2022), to make learners become engaged, participative, contributing and active while learning the language (Fabríz *et al.*, 2021). Since technology took its pivotal role of the changes, the teaching and learning can become *the metaverse*, a digital space that uses advanced technology and making internet as a single universe where learners meet from across the globe using virtual and augmented reality.

The CLA of English supervision and teaching and learning process

Based on the participant's responses in the fourth layer of CLA (myth/metaphor), there can be profound stories, poignant dimensions of problems, or paradoxes that elicit visual images; in this case, the two (English Instructional supervision and Teaching and Learning) are compared by the researcher to "*international standards*". Using the participants' narratives to unpack the desired future, the researcher devised a metaphor describing the alternative future for English supervision and the teaching and learning process. However, it is less concerned with the particular future but with opening spaces to expand the scenarios presented (Inayatullah, 2005).

Deeping: *International standards*. Both instructional supervision and English teaching and learning can be compared to *international standards*. The metaphor that resonates the most revealed that instructional supervision is an exam/a test, foreseeing supervision has regularly assessed standards to see if the functions fit the current set-up. At the same time, English teaching and learning is a globe.

International standards are a document developed with the consensus of experts from different countries and are globally approved and recognized (Shandu, 2022) for sustainable development. Samples of this are ISO standards. These standards should be based on the results of experiences and results of science, especially during the two-year educational gap brought on by the pandemic.

Conclusions

The combined results accepted the assumption of this study that the supervision and instructional techniques used during face-to-face classes and distance learning diverged. This assumption influenced the implementation of the curriculum and the student's performance in English. Moreover, it acknowledged that the past and present practices helped determine the *ideal alternative futures*. Based on the results, the following conclusions are advanced:

- 1) The English Instructional supervisors saw their alternative future in the course of *an exam or a test*. In the next five years, it can become a first-aid tool kit, and after then, it becomes an AI-generated supervision as it faces innovation.
- 2) The English teachers saw their alternative future as *a globe*, using English as the tool for progress and innovation. The teachers' efficacy and efficiency in the use of language will help learners acquire the Language Arts and Multiliteracies Curriculum skills for them to become global citizens- able to communicate, build relationships and propose development around the globe. In the next 5 years, it can become a "Roblox", which will bring all teachers and learners all together through a play (centralized teaching-learning); as soon as it becomes successful, the teaching and learning will become possible in the metaverse, an ideal future world using technologies with the use of virtual reality.
- 3) The future of supervision, teaching, and learning can be gleaned in a collective metaphor "*the international standards*". These standards are based on the results of experiences and results of science and research during the pandemic. Such metaphors can become the basis for open discussion and might help foresight practitioners for individual research or workshop settings (Simone, 2004). This can lead to the "*school of virtual reality*", where AI- generated (supervision) and *metaverse* (teaching and learning) play an explicit role in supervision and the teaching and learning process.

Recommendations

Based on the summary of findings and conclusions presented, the following recommendations are drawn:

- 1) The Bureau of Curriculum Development should continue the initiative to revisit the Language Arts and Multiliteracies Curriculum standards to check its relevance to the current changes brought about by the shift of modalities and to accelerate the delivery of the curriculum. They should also update policies that give clear direction to English teaching and learning supervision and on the upskilling of instructional leaders and teachers with proper and appropriate technology integration that suits their needs today and in the future.
 - 2) The English supervisors should include the Information Technology (IT) infrastructure as the foundation for seamless operation which will be embedded in the Supervisory Program. Likewise, in coordination with the guidance office, regular Social-emotional learning (SEL) activities and programs that address and help the different stakeholders understand the role of technology and social media platforms in language learning should be made.
 - 3) The English supervisors should continuously work together with the English teachers in creating academic programs such as remedial and enrichment activities to assess, help, and provide an extension of learning, especially in the acquisition of reading skills and other competencies found in the Language Arts and Multiliteracies Curriculum by utilizing effective and suitable strategies, techniques, and technology.
 - 4) The school's English department should strengthen the vertical articulation of English subjects from kinder to senior high school to identify gaps and fill these breaches through instructional-related programs created by the team.
 - 5) Future researchers should engage in studies to help schools, academic institutions, and other establishments improve and see their ultimate path to progress, addressing current problems and re-creating transformative spaces of alternative futures.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher ensured the respondents' participation was voluntary and free from threat or prejudice. All the participants were given an informed consent form and asked to sign it if they agreed to participate in the study. The informed consent contained relevant information about the study and was read to the participants before the interview. Since the interview was recorded, permission was asked from the participants before clicking the record button. No other questions far from the purpose of the study were asked aside from the prepared queries, and if the questions were replaced or rephrased for clarification, they were still about the main point of the interview. Participants were also guaranteed privacy and confidentiality, so their real names were not used; a pseudonym was given to them even during the interview. The raw data were kept confidential and can

only be accessed by the researcher. The data will be deleted three (3) years after the study's publishing date.

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REFERENCES

- Akyildiz S., & Ahmed K. (2021). An overview of qualitative research and focus group discussion. *International Journal of Academic Research in Education*. DOI:10.17985/ijare.866762. <https://tinyurl.com/yjrjre83>
- Alamri, W. (2019). Effectiveness of qualitative research methods: Interviews and diaries. *International Journal of English and Cultural Studies*. Vo. 2, No. 1. ISSN 2575-811X, E-ISSN 2575-8101. <https://tinyurl.com/aeyawevy>
- Al-Hashmi, S. (2021). A study on impact of the sudden change to online education on the motivation of higher education students. *Canadian Center of Science and Education*. <https://tinyurl.com/yrfs56m4>
- Allen, K.E. (2020). Viewing leadership through a systems lens (in a time of pandemic). *International Leadership Association*. <https://tinyurl.com/2ybtj774>

- Ancho, I. (2021). Education policies and COVID-19 in the Philippines' observations and inputs. *Interdisciplinary Research review*. Vol. 16, No. 4. Pages 1-8.
<https://tinyurl.com/mrywu6zj>
- Ariffin, N. A. N., Ramli, N., Nik Badrul Alam, N. M. F. H., Yusof, Y., & Suparlan, A. (2022). Effectiveness of gamification in teaching and learning mathematics. *Journal on Mathematics Education*, 13(1), 173–190.
<https://doi.org/10.22342/jme.v13i1.pp173-190>
- Ayandoja, A.C., Aina, B.C., & Idowu, A.F. (2017). Academic supervision as a correlate of students' academic performance in secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Educational Policy Research and Review*, Vo. 4, pp 8-13.
<https://tinyurl.com/3v7369h3>
- Bailey, K. (2006). *Language teacher supervision: A case-based approach*. Cambridge University press. <https://tinyurl.com/3scpa7wt>
- Belias, D., Sdrolas, L., Nikolaos, K., & Koutiva, M. (2013). Traditional teaching methods vs. teaching through the application of information and communication technologies in the accounting field: Quo vadis? *European Scientific Journal*, 9(28), 73-101. <https://tinyurl.com/mu5z2efn>
- Bim-Bad, B.M., & Egorova, L.I. (2016). Interaction between philosophy of education and teaching practice. *International Journal of Environmental and Science Education*. Vol. 11, No.10, 3385-3393. <https://tinyurl.com/59fz9b3p>
- Boholano, H., Cajes, R., & Boholano, G.S. (2021). Technology based teaching and learning in junior high school. *Research in Pedagogy*, Vol. 11, No.1, pp. 98-107.
<https://tinyurl.com/2rsb3wnv>
- Brock, J.D., Beach, D.M., Musselwhite, M., & Holder, I. (2021). Instructional supervision and the COVID-19 Pandemic: Perspectives from principals. *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*, 11(1). <https://tinyurl.com/49pearjn>
- Buenaventura, D.U. (2013). Turn-over rate of teachers in private basic education schools: Input to administrative program development. *ResearchGate*.
<https://tinyurl.com/y6f5c7be>
- Burch, B. (2019). Class Size in Online Courses: What the Research Says. Quality Matters. <https://www.qualitymatters.org/qa-resources/resource-center/articles-resources/research-on-class-size>
- Bussey, S.I. (2008). *Alternative educational futures: Pedagogies for emergent worlds*.
<https://tinyurl.com/yetnrc9z>
- Cano, E.V., & Garcia, M.L. (2013). ICT strategies and tools for the improvement of instructional supervision. the virtual supervision. *Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*. <https://tinyurl.com/yt8t5rx>
- Carballo, C.V. (2018). *Delphi method and CLA*. Academia. <https://tinyurl.com/ybth6nmz>
- Cennimo, D. (2023). Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19). *Medscape*.
<https://tinyurl.com/nhy9ut4v>
- Crystal, D. (2003). *English as a Global Language* (2nd ed.). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511486999>
- Davidson, S. (2020). Intersectionality: A Tool for Using Causal Layered Analysis in Education. *Journal of Future Studies*.
[https://doi.org/10.6531/JFS.202012_25\(2\).0007](https://doi.org/10.6531/JFS.202012_25(2).0007)

- DeJonckheere M., & Vaughn L.M. (2019). Semistructured interviewing in primary care research: A balance of relationship and rigour. *Fam Med Com Health*;7:e000057. <https://tinyurl.com/39kvmwe9>
- Department of Education (DepEd, 2020). *Learning opportunities shall be available the basic education learning continuity plan in the time of COVID-19*. 2-4. <https://tinyurl.com/3av7v72p>
- DepEd. (2020). DepEd recognizes mental health and wellbeing of personnel, conducts MHPSS provisions. <https://tinyurl.com/2p88f2zj>
- Demirbilek, M., Talan, T., & Alzouebi, K. (2022). An examination of the factors and challenges to adopting gamification in English foreign language teaching. *International Journal of Technology in Education*, 5(4), 654–668. <https://doi.org/10.46328/ijte.358>
- Duran, J.A., Gutierrez, K.S., & Ramirez, Y.A. (2021). Learning strategies and their influence on foreign language skills: A literature review from the Oxford taxonomy. *MEXTESOL Journal*. Vo. 46, No. 2. ISSN: 23959908. <https://tinyurl.com/3w58bsc2>
- Eisenring, M. a. A., & Margana, M. (2019). THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHER – STUDENTS INTERACTION IN COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING (CLT). *Prasasti/UNS Journal of Language Studies*, 4(1), 46. <https://doi.org/10.20961/prasasti.v4i1.17052>
- Esteron, M.A. (2021). Equity in online learning amidst pandemic in the Philippines. *International Journal of English Literature and Social Sciences*. Vol. 6, Issue 5. <https://tinyurl.com/mtf3p3ua>
- Fabriz, S., Mendzheritskaya, J., & Stehle, S. (2021). Impact of synchronous and asynchronous settings of online teaching and learning in higher education on students' learning experience during COVID-19. *Frontiers in Psychology*. <https://tinyurl.com/4txdxmvy>
- Fendi, H., Hanafi, I., Monia, F.A., Sudarman, M., Taufiq A., & Putri, R.E. (2021). Online-based academic supervision during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1779, 012027. <https://tinyurl.com/2p8skupw>
- Fink, A. (2010). *Survey research methods*. Editor(s): Penelope Peterson, Eva Baker, Barry McGaw, International Encyclopedia of Education (Third Edition), Pages 152-160, ISBN 9780080448947. <https://tinyurl.com/mt2dya2d>
- Frey, B. B. (2018). *The SAGE Encyclopedia of Educational Research, Measurement, and Evaluation*. SAGE Publications, Inc. eBooks. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781506326139>
- Gamage, D., Adams, D., McCornack, A. (2009). *How does a school leader's role influence student achievements? A review of research findings and best practices*. <https://tinyurl.com/4sa5j7bf>
- Geary, C. (2020). *Lessons from pandemic teacher candidate supervision*. Issues in teacher education. Caddo Gap Press. <https://tinyurl.com/ywwc4ap4>
- Gil-Aciron, L.G. (2022). Benefits of gamification in second language learning. *ResearchGate*. <https://tinyurl.com/39e9dx7e>
- Griffin, T. M. (2020). Centering Graduate Students' Research Projects in Data Management Education: a pilot program. *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.7710/2162-3309.2365>

- Groth, R. E., & Bergner, J. A. (2005). PRE-SERVICE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS' METAPHORS FOR THE CONCEPT OF STATISTICAL SAMPLE. *Statistics Education Research Journal*, 4(2), 27–42. <https://doi.org/10.52041/serj.v4i2.513>
- Hakim, S., Sowiyah, U., Fitriyanti, Z., & Pedarna, R. (2021). *The effect of academic supervision in improving teacher performance. A literature review*. DOI 10.4108/eai.16-10-2020.2305197. <https://tinyurl.com/2dznce39>
- Heming, A.L. (2008). *Multiple intelligences in the classroom*. Honors College Capstone Experience/Thesis Projects. Paper 138. <https://tinyurl.com/bdfracpk>
- Hogan, M., & Bruce, B. (2013). What's next? The future of progressivism as an "infinite succession of presents". *International Association of Educators*. ISSN: 1554-5210. <https://tinyurl.com/yc94nfdc>
- Hoyla, E., (2021). *Secondary school students' lived experiences on self-learning modules: A cross case analysis*. University of Southeastern Philippines. Pages 104-106.
- Hurry, J. & Russel, T. (2022). An evaluation of professional supervision for teachers. Institute of Education. <https://tinyurl.com/442zbezK>
- Hwa, Y. Kaffenberger, M., & Silberstein, J. (2020). Aligning levels of instruction with goals and the needs of students (ALIGNs): Varied approaches, common principles. *RISE Insight Series*. 2020/022. <https://tinyurl.com/34r2xeYe>
- Inayatullah, S. & Baldwin, P. (2021). *Communicating the future: Foresight as mindfulness*. *Journal of Future Studies*, pp. 91-100. <https://tinyurl.com/ch6uj7vz>
- Inayatullah, S. (2002). *Reductionism or layered complexity? The futures of futures studies*. Pages 295-302, <https://tinyurl.com/4x574tmu>
- Inayatullah, S. (2004). *The Causal Layered Analysis (CLA) Reader. Theory and case studies of an integrative and transformative methodology*. Tamkang University press. <https://tinyurl.com/3apmczn8>
- Inayatullah, S. (2008). Six pillars: Futures thinking for transforming. *Foresight Journal*, Vol. 10 NO. 1 2008, pp. 4-21. <https://tinyurl.com/23dcuwvp>
- Inayatullah, S. (2013). *Future Studies: Theories and methods*. <https://tinyurl.com/3bzn4stx>
- Inayatullah, S. (2014) *Causal Layered Analysis (CLA) defined. Metafuture*. <https://tinyurl.com/ncajfy5e>
- Inayatullah, S. (2019). *Causal layered Analysis: A four-level approach to alternative futures relevance and use in foresight. Futuribles*. <https://tinyurl.com/2ns7ekh7>
- Inayatullah, S. (2020). *Co-creating educational futures: Contradictions between the emerging future and the walled past*. UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization). <https://tinyurl.com/2p9s8nwn>
- Inayatullah, S. (2022). *Anticipation to Emancipation: Toward a stage theory of the uses of the future*. UNESCO. First Edition. ISBN: 978-0-6454283-0-8. <https://tinyurl.com/mue28t3n>
- Inayatullah, S., & Gidley, J. (2000). Trends transforming the universities in this century: virtualize, disappear, or transform. *On the Horizon*. Strategic planning resource for education professionals. Vol. 8, No. 2. <https://tinyurl.com/4t4fyp6m>

- Ince, Z. (2021). Research on technology management and its application in schools in the pandemic period. *The Turkish Online Journal of Education Technology*. Vo. 21, Issue 2. oguta
- Istiningsih, E., & Widodo, S. (2020). Academic supervision to improve teachers' readiness in utilizing information and communication technology in vocational high schools. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*.
<https://tinyurl.com/ypd3yur5>
- Jambangan, E. (2015). *Structural equation model predicting students' reading attitude and performance*. A Thesis, University of Southeastern Philippines.
- K to 12 English Curriculum Guide (2016). Department of Education.
<https://tinyurl.com/5ea6m8kr>
- Kapur, R. (2018). Rapport building. *ResearchGate*. <https://tinyurl.com/yfkxw8d4>
- Karkar-Esperat, T. M. (2018). International graduate students' challenges and learning experiences in online classes. *Journal of International Students*, 8(4).
<https://doi.org/10.32674/jis.v8i4.227>
- Kayaoğlu, M. N. (2012). The Use of Mother Tongue in Foreign Language Teaching from Teachers' Practice and Perspective. *Pamukkale Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 32, 25–35. <https://doi.org/10.9779/puje492>
- Khaef, E., & Karimnia, A. (2021). The effects of Implementing Clinical Supervision model on supervisors' teaching perspectives and Qualifications: A case study in an EFL context. *Education Research International*, 2021, 1–11.
<https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/6138873>
- Kipruto, S.S. (2009). The effects of supervision on academic performance in secondary schools in Ollessos division, Nandi East District. <https://tinyurl.com/3cph86zx>
- Kolanchery, G. (2015). ANALYTICAL COMPONENTS OF MORPHOLOGY IN LINGUISTICS. *Global English-Oriented Research Journal (GEORJ)*, 1.
<https://tinyurl.com/mur6njt8>
- Korhani, L. (2021). *Flexible leadership in a multigenerational workforce*.
<https://tinyurl.com/3ynh6tas>
- Kumar, A.S. (2021). Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on teaching and learning in health professional education: A mixed methods study protocol. *BMC Med Educ*, 439. <https://tinyurl.com/2pydybss>
- Kush, J., Badillo-Goicoechea, E., Musci, R., & Stuart, E. (2022). Teachers' mental health during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Educ Res*. 2022 doi: 10.3102/0013189X221134281. <https://tinyurl.com/y9r2p9az>
- Kwee, C. (2022). To teach or not to teach: An international study of language teachers' experiences of online teaching during the COVID-19 pandemic. *SN Computer Science, Springer Link*. Vol.3, Article. 416. <https://tinyurl.com/4tyjs2ta>
- Lasater, K. (2016). School Leader Relationships: The Need for Explicit Training on Rapport, Trust, and Communication. *Journal of School Administration Research and Development*, 1(2). Retrieved from
<https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1158155.pdf>
- Lee, J., & Tippet, P. (2021). Looking back to move forward: Understanding progressive education in the 21st century. *Journal of Applied Learning in Higher Education*.
<https://tinyurl.com/5a5y4xuk>

- Li, L. (2022). Factors affecting the student performance during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Scientific Research an Academic Publisher*, 10(7). <https://tinyurl.com/4p7u3h4c>
- Lie, A., Mina Tamah, S., Gozali, I., Retno Triwidayati, K., Sari Diah Utami, T., & Jemadi, F. (2020). Secondary school language teachers' online learning engagement during the COVID-19 pandemic in Indonesia. *Journal of Information Technology Education: Research*, 19, 803-832. <https://tinyurl.com/33mdmnac>
- Mahyoob, M. (2020). Challenges of e-learning during the COVID-19 pandemic experienced by EFL learners. *Arab World English Journal*, 11(4), 351-362. <https://tinyurl.com/y939wnxd>
- Mann, A. (2020). *How the COVID-19 pandemic is changing education: A perspective from Saudi Arabia*. OECD. <https://tinyurl.com/2se9pu5b>
- Mette, I. (2020). Reflections on Supervision in the Time of COVID-19. *Journal of Educational Supervision*, 3 (3). <https://doi.org/10.31045/jes.3.3.1>
- Meurs, P., Note, N., & Aerts, D. (2011). The "Globe" of globalization. *Kritike*, 5(2), 10–25. <https://doi.org/10.25138/5.2.a.2>
- Mhishi, M., & Gwizangwe, I. (2022). Towards a sustainable technology-enhanced supervision and assessment of teaching practice: A pilot case of an e-Supervision model at a university in Zimbabwe. *International Journal of Education and Development using information and Communication technology*, Vol. 18, Issue 2, pp. 68-79. <https://tinyurl.com/2xwa5rsz>
- Middleton, F. (2023). *The 4 types of reliability in research: Definitions & examples*. <https://tinyurl.com/5fm27zeh>
- Millojevic, I. & Inayatullah, S. (2015). Narrative foresight. Elsevier Ltd. *Futures*, 75, pp 151-162. <https://tinyurl.com/kewjncc2>
- Milton, L. E., & Landon, L. E. (2019). Student Perspectives on the Immediate Feedback Assessment Technique. *Journal of Occupational Therapy Education*, 3 (3). <https://doi.org/10.26681/jote.2019.030301>
- Mishra, L. (2016, June). Focus group discussion in qualitative research. *TechnoLearn* Vol. 6: No. 1: p. 1-5. <https://tinyurl.com/yv4wdtkb>
- Mohammed, M.O. (2014). Planning the teacher as in loco parentis for an effective school system. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*. ISSN 2039-2117. <https://tinyurl.com/24x35pmk>
- Morgan, H. (2021). *Howard Gardner's multiple intelligences theory and his ideas on promoting creativity*. In F. Reisman (Ed.), *Celebrating Giants and Trailblazers: A-Z of Who's Who in Creativity Research and Related Fields* (pp.124-141). London, UK: KIE Publications. <https://tinyurl.com/39e9dx7e>
- National Education Technology. (2016). Reimagining the role of technology in education. <https://tinyurl.com/yckj5rvw>
- Ngole, D., & Mkulu, D., (2021). The role of school heads' supervision in improving quality of teaching and learning: A case of public secondary school in Ilemela District Mwanza Tanzania. *International Journal of English Literature and Social Sciences*, Vol-6, Issue-1. ISSN: 2456-7620. <https://tinyurl.com/2ejry8xn>
- Nikade, E.C. (2022). *Language teaching and learning in post COVID-19 teaching and learning*. <https://tinyurl.com/yc2bfnya>

- Nikolopoulou, K. (2022). Online education in early primary years: Teachers' practices and experiences during COVID-19 Pandemic. *Education Sciences*.
<https://tinyurl.com/2wbwp3ta>
- OECD. (2015). Education policy outlook 2015: Making reforms Happen. OECD Publishing. ISBN 978-92-64-22544. <https://tinyurl.com/39p8mu2b>
- OECD. (2018). Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) results from PISA 2018. <https://tinyurl.com/4e679etp>
- OECD. (2018). The future we want. *OECD Learning Framework 2030*, 3.
<https://tinyurl.com/yx8xsu4v>
- OECD. (2020). Back to the future of education: Four OECD scenarios for schooling.
<https://tinyurl.com/2p8j966h>
- Oguta, P.A., Getange, K.N., & Juma, S. (2019). Teacher supervision influence on students' academic achievement in secondary school education in Migori County, Kenya. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*. Vol. 4, Issue 5. ISSN No: 2456-2165. <https://tinyurl.com/yh5upf2t>
- Okinyi, N. P., Kwaba, J. G., & Nyabuto, N. N. (2015). The role of leaders in transforming learners and learning in the higher learning institutions in Kenya. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(25), 105–116.
<http://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1078527.pdf>
- Olivia-Dumitrina, N., Casanovas, M., & Capdevila, Y. (2019). Academic Writing and the Internet: Cyber-Plagiarism amongst University Students. *Journal of New Approaches in Educational Research*, 8(2), 112.
<https://doi.org/10.7821/naer.2019.7.407>
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (2009). Teaching practices, teachers' beliefs and attitudes. *Creating Effective Teaching and Learning Environments: First Results from TALIS*, 87-135. <https://tinyurl.com/39cwnuyb>
- Othman, Y., & Mydin, A.A. (2022). The role, strategy, and challenges of instructional supervision of the COVID-19 Pandemic Era: A systematic literature review. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 12(7), 1059-1070. doi: <https://tinyurl.com/ywpe7sdt>
- Prihatin, S., Fitria, H., & Fitriani, Y. (2021). The role of the academic supervision of school heads in improving teacher performance in the pandemic time. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, Vol. 565.
<https://tinyurl.com/5h9cc7et>
- Rao, S. P. (2019). The Importance of Speaking Skills in English Classrooms. *Alford Council of International English & Literature Journal*, 2, 6-18.
- Riedy, C. (2008). An integral extension of causal layered analysis. *Futures*, 40(2), 150-159. <https://tinyurl.com/4nwbzzsr>
- Rilliard, M. (2020). Adaptability 2.0: Tackling the challenge of the COVID-19 crisis. *Second Language Research & Practice*, 1(1), 179182. <https://tinyurl.com/2p9f2cuf>
- Rochon, J. (2021). *Pandemic school leadership: Lessons learned and implications for post-covid schooling*. <https://tinyurl.com/5x9brkt5>
- Rogerson, S. (2021). For the record: the evolution of acceptable digital technology. *Journal of Information, Communication & Ethics in Society*, 19(4), 425–432.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/jices-11-2021-142>

- Romanes, M. A. J., & Viniegas, S. (2018). Differences among Generational Groups of Teachers in a Public School District in Their Practice of 21st Century Teaching-Learning Skills. The International Academic Forum. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/58zzkdhw>
- Satharathana, T. (2021). English teaching and learning in the new normal in the Thai education context. *Journal of Industrial Education*, 20(3). <https://tinyurl.com/2y8t793k>
- Schleicher, A., & Reimers, F. (2020). The impact of COVID-19 on education: insights from Education at a Glance 2020. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/bddewww7>
- Shandu, L. M. (2022). What International Standards are, the purpose of the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) and how ISO standards help to achieve the Global Goals for Sustainable Development. ResearchGate. <https://tinyurl.com/2f8wmsze>
- Simone, S.D. (2004). Causal layered analysis: A 'cookbook' approach. (S. Inayatullah, Ed.) *The Causal Layered Analysis (CLA) Reader: Theory and Case Studies of an Integrative and Transformative Methodology*, Tamkang University Press, Tamsui. <https://tinyurl.com/yu3drsdj>
- Singh, J., Steele, K., & Singh, L. (2021). Combining the best of online and face-to-face learning: Hybrid and blended learning approach for COVID-19, post vaccine, & post-pandemic world. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, 50(2), 140-171. <https://tinyurl.com/ynmkzuxp>
- Sirait, S. (2016). Does teacher quality affect student achievement? An empirical study in Indonesia. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(27). <https://tinyurl.com/yfzwhhz6>
- Stamatis, P.J. (2021). Impact of COVID-19 on teaching and classroom management: Thoughts based on current situation and the role of communication. *European Journal of Education and Pedagogy*, 2(1). doi:10.24018/ejedu.2021.2.1.48. <https://tinyurl.com/3kj2v6k9>
- Stauffer, B. (2022). Top 7 blended learning strategies for CTE. *Career and technical Education*. <https://tinyurl.com/2ja4xnw9>
- Su, W., Qi, Q., & Yuan, S. (2022). A moderated mediation model of academic supervisor developmental feedback and postgraduate student creativity: Evidence from China. *Behavioral Sciences*. <https://tinyurl.com/rnwhct8z>
- Suarez, Z.N. (2022). English language teaching and learning during the COVID-19 pandemic: A study in Manizales High Schools. Repositorio Ucaldas. <https://tinyurl.com/bdfzhuec>
- Tagare Jr., R. (2023). Back to in-person classes in the Philippine basic education: Threading the opportunities and limitations in the teaching of physical education. *Federación Española de Asociaciones de Docentes de Educación Física*. ISSN: 1579-1726. <https://tinyurl.com/24t6euku>
- Talebian, S., & Talebian, H. (2018). The application of causal layered analysis to understand the present conditions and possible futures of media and politics in Iran. *European Journal of Futures Research*. <https://tinyurl.com/2vduhkjj>
- Tapio, P., & Heinonen S. (2018). *Focused future from Finland*. Vol. 10, Issue 2. <https://tinyurl.com/43wve7y9>

- Thomas, S. (2016). Future ready learning reimagining the role of technology in reeducation. *Office of Educational Technology*. <https://tinyurl.com/e3fuzchh>
- UNESCO. (2015). Reimagining our futures together, anew social contract for education. *Report from the International commission on the Futures of education*, 186. <https://tinyurl.com/dcpjf5e5>
- Villegas, L., & Garcia, A. (2022). *Educating English learners during the pandemic, insights from experts, advocates, and practitioners*. <https://tinyurl.com/44uwfvjt>
- Warren, L. L. (2021). The importance of teacher leadership skills in the classroom. *Education Journal*, 10(1), 8. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.edu.20211001.12>
- Watkins, N.A. (2022). *The role of teachers in educational policymaking. Literature reviews in education and human services*. Vo. 1, Issue 1, pp. 1-23. <https://tinyurl.com/yk3bapv7>
- Wiyono, B., Wedi, A., Ulfa, S., & Putra, A. (2021). *The use of information and communication technology (ICT) in the implementation of instructional supervision and its effect on teachers' instructional process quality*. *Advances in Baseband Signal Processing, Circuit Designs, and Communications. Information* 12(11), 475. MDPI AG. <https://tinyurl.com/fk4r7bkk>
- Yulianti, H., Prestiadi, D., & Imron, A. (2021). Implementation of academic supervision in improving teachers teaching performance in the COVID-19 pandemic era at elementary school. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, Volume 601. 7th International Conference on Education and Technology. <https://tinyurl.com/ymn6uzr8>
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